

D2.3 : Report on cluster-specific societal, geographical, economic and environmental frameworks

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D2.3: Report on cluster-specific societal, geographical, economic and environmental frameworks

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Disclaimer

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Summary

Chapter 1. Introduction presents the structure of the deliverable and the link with the task 2.3.

Chapter 2. Profile and expertise of cluster members provides information on the profiles of the three clusters' members, organisations that are key actors of the Research and Innovation (R&I) regional ecosystems and joined forces to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation in their territory. Each cluster is composed of a leading organisation (Fondazione Giannino Bassetti in Lombardy, Science for Change in Catalonia and BE participation in Brussels-Capital), specialised in RRI processes including: policy recommendations, coordination of participative processes in R&I and science engagement, multistakeholder (quadruple helix) engagement and citizen engagement. Each cluster also involves representatives of the regional government and/or a public agency in charge of R&I for the region and responsible for the coordination and the monitoring of regional Smart Specialisation Strategies (Regione Lombardia in Lombardy, Generalitat de Catalunya - GDPECR in Catalonia and Innoviris in Brussels-Capital). Each cluster involves an additional partner for the representation of the quadruple helix and local key actors for the effectiveness of quadruple helix participative processes: Finlombarda – Finanziaria per lo Sviluppo della Lombardia S.p.A. - a financial company owned by Regione Lombardia, Opensystems, a research group founded by the University of Barcelona and the Earth and Life Institute (ELI), a research institute of the Université Catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain) in Belgium.

Chapter 3. Research and Innovation ecosystems in the TRANSFORM regions presents the information gathered by each cluster and the work done so far at each cluster level. For the Lombardy region, the main activities have been related to Participatory Research Agenda Setting in the design of the PST; Citizen Engagement in S3 (implementation); and Regional RRI performance experimental evaluation. The main outputs are online mutual learning exercises to identify and map RRI activities of the Region, embedment of RRI in objectives of the next S3 plan and design and implementation of a capacity building exercise. For the Catalonia region, the main activities were to define the role of the local Think Tank which was launched in June 2020 to reflect on the potential of RRI and citizen science, and an overview analysis of R&I Catalan ecosystem. For the Brussels-Capital region, the main activities were to define the role of the local Think Tank to support the cluster's pilot activities and to help with the assessment of R&I activities looking at the impact on the local public good; an overview analysis of R&I Brussels-Capital ecosystem; and a reflection process with the cluster members exploring the broad topic of circular economy, preparing the work of analysis of community needs and challenges to address. In addition, each cluster presents the latest development of Smart Specialisation Strategies and regional R&I programmes, as all three regions are in the process of renewing their S3 plans.

Chapter 4. Results of SWOT analysis presents the outcomes of the regional SWOT analysis run in each cluster, as well as what has emerged from the collaborative Map & Reflect workshop. The objectives of the SWOT analysis at each cluster level were to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that the cluster could encounter to achieve the overall objective of the project taking into account the regional contexts; develop strategies to anticipate negative elements; identify skills possibly needed to support clusters' members; reflect on directional possibilities of the project within the S3 and RRI framework. The SWOT analysis carried-out at each cluster level is presented in the deliverable.

For Lombardy, the strengths include the fact that the regional authority is dedicated to RRI, is reflexive and willing to listen to multistakeholders' voices; and a long list of concrete strengths directly connected to RRI actions or dimensions. The weaknesses have been turned into suggestions for actions e.g. to include RRI terminology in the regional R&I calls and introduce a budget for public communication in the R&I regional calls. Opportunities include two main groups: opportunities connected to RRI in general; and specific opportunities for the Lombardy Region. Finally, two general risks have also been identified including the understanding of RRI for industrial partners and the challenges of citizen engagement. In Catalonia, the strengths include several elements on the already good uptake of RRI by the regional authority and the dynamism and quantity of citizen science initiatives in the region. As per the weaknesses, the elements are grouped in themes including the elements related to RRI (lack of knowledge and measurement in the region); to quadruple helix engagement (lack of platforms and participatory tradition); and to citizen science. The opportunities include the integration of RRI in the next S3 of the region and the diversity of the R&I ecosystem. Finally, the threats involve the COVID 19 crisis, possible resistance of citizens, the government priorities for the economy and the excess of confidence in the results that quadruple helix transformative processes can lead to an early abandonment of initiatives. For the Brussels-Capital region, the strengths include elements related to the cluster composition; the EU dimension of the project; the theme of circular economy & innovation; the methodology; the citizen-centered approach and decision-making & policy formulation. The weaknesses include the scale of the action, limited understanding of large-scale dynamics; making sure the bottom-up approach is really used; and the fact that the work in the field is still in experimentation. The opportunities are related to the dynamic and intense regional social network and the number of potential partners. Finally, the risks are related to the COVID 19 crisis; the project sustainability; and the contradiction between ambition and reality. In addition to the individual cluster SWOT analysis a comparative exercise was carried out collaboratively.

Chapter 5. Societal, economic, geographical and environmental frameworks in which the participatory actions will be developed by each cluster. A key step for the TRANSFORM project is to

understand the societal needs of the citizens that will be involved in participatory processes as well as the economic, geographical and environmental frameworks of the R&I ecosystems in each of the three regions. The participatory processes in the three clusters will rely on quadruple helix engagement with a particular focus on citizen engagement. To be able to implement these participatory activities, the clusters performed an intensive reflection work to understand the societal needs and the economic, geographical and environmental frameworks particular to their regions and their R&I ecosystem. Some key elements that have an influence on or need to be taken into account in the choice of cluster activities are presented there.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable gathers the outcomes of task 2.3 REFLECT that was implemented from M1 to M11, led by BE participation (BEpart) involving all partners. The aim of this task was for partners to map and collect relevant data on their regional R&I strategies and to deploy reflective practices to analyse their experience and actions, contributing to the general aim of WP2, namely to engage in a continuous learning process.

The outcome of the mapping and collection of relevant data is presented in two sections:

- Chapter 2. Profile and expertise of cluster members provides information on the profiles of the three clusters' members, organisations that are key actors of the R&I regional ecosystems and joined forces to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation in their territory.
- Chapter 3. Research and Innovation ecosystems in the TRANSFORM regions presents the information gathered by each cluster and the work done so far at each cluster level.

The main analysis performed within each cluster, the reflection sessions and the SWOT analysis had the objective to help regional clusters to reflect on their place within the larger societal, geographical, economic and environmental framework while planning cluster activities. A map&reflect workshop was held to share critical elements identified by each cluster within the SWOT analysis, and define collaborative propositions on how to improve the openness and inclusiveness of regional R&I ecosystems.

The outcomes of these analysis are presented in two chapters:

- Chapter 4. Results of SWOT analysis including the regional SWOT analysis ran in each cluster and the results of the Map & Reflect workshop done collaboratively.
- Chapter 5. Societal, economic, geographical and environmental frameworks in which the participatory actions will be developed carried out by each cluster.

2. Profile and expertise of cluster members

As part of the collection of relevant data on regional R&I strategies, an important point was to describe and place the key actor each cluster is composed of in the R&I ecosystem.

Each region represented in the TRANSFORM project is composed of multistakeholders cluster with regional public authorities, academic partners and organisations experts in participatory methodologies. They are described below.

2.1 Lombardy Cluster members profiles

TRANSFORM regional cluster of Lombardy counts three members and a third party.

Fondazione Giannino Bassetti (FGB)

Coordinator of the TRANSFORM project and cluster leader for Lombardy.

FGB) was founded in 1994 and has promoted responsibility in innovation within the technosciences, entrepreneurship and governance since more than 25 years, acting as a pioneer CSO in fostering the concept and the practice of RRI. In 2004 FGB promoted the first Consensus Conference in Italy, aiming at regulating the usage of GMOs in Lombardy Region territory. The result of such activity was the change of the Lombardy statute on Innovation (article 10.3), stating the introduction of “proper procedures and tools to implement Responsible Innovation when deciding on techno-scientific innovation in Lombardy”.

Mobilizing and consolidating communities of practice, Fondazione Giannino Bassetti promotes cooperation between the drivers of innovation, weaving networks between research sites, industrial players, civil society and institutions, creating transverse and cutting-edge relationships.

In 2015, FGB entity was modified in Foundation of Participation - as supported by Italian law- and the Lombardy Regional Government ratified its participation in 2016. Thanks to this close relationship, since 2017 Bassetti Foundation coordinates the activities of the Lombardy Region Forum on Research and Innovation, introduced by Regional Law 29/2016, and composed of 10 highly qualified experts in the relationship between science and society, selected through an international public procedure. The aim of the Forum is to strengthen regional actions on open and responsible innovation at local and at international level, thanks to technology assessment, public consultations on research agenda setting, social innovation and open science initiatives and strategies.

FGB is also an affiliate member of Virtual Institute of Responsible Innovation, the largest community devoted to discuss and promote reflections and practices of RRI. Furthermore, FGB is within the

Editorial Board of the “Journal of Responsible Innovation”, the first journal fully devoted to this theme. In 2018, Fondazione Bassetti was one of the few CSOs participating in the AI4People Initiative, where contributed to assess and revise the “Ethical Framework for a Good AI Society”. FGB is currently accepted member of the EU AI Alliance.

FGB is contributing to shape the R&I policies towards a more open, inclusive and responsible approach, both at the local and the international level. FGB has participated in several European H2020 projects and has a consolidated experience with public and stakeholder engagement. The Foundation is also in charge of the management of the Regional Forum for Research and Innovation, an independent advisory group introduced by Lombardy Region in 2016, thanks to the Regional Law no. 29/2016 “Lombardy is Research and Innovation”.

Lombardy Region (LR) - Directorate General for Research, Innovation, University, Export and Internationalisation of Enterprises

The Directorate supports research in emerging sectors, promoting the transfer of results to the market, and supporting innovation throughout LR, to increase the well-being of citizens and the competitiveness of the economic-social system.

Supporting research in emerging strategic sectors, promoting the transfer of results to the market and supporting innovation throughout the Lombardy region, to increase the well-being of citizens and the competitiveness of the economic-social system, are the objectives that the Lombardy Region entrusts to the General Directorate Research, Innovation, University, Export and Internationalization.

The initiatives and interventions are part of the framework designed by Regional Law no. 29 of 23 November 2016 "Lombardia is Research and Innovation", which structures the governance of the regional research system (through the Three-year Strategic Program for Research, Innovation and Technology Transfer), tracing the priority development lines in this area, identifying the enabling factors to strengthen the innovative capacity of the territory and strengthening the research and innovation infrastructures for technology and knowledge transfer, in connection with national and European policies.

A continuous dialogue with the local actors of the R&I process (companies, citizens, universities and research centres, technological clusters, etc.) is central in Lombardy R&I policies.

Lombardy Region participates actively in different interregional networking activities such as the Vanguard Initiative, the political network of European regions committed to promote the implementation of the Smart Specialisation Strategy and S3 Thematic Platforms launched by European Commission. Lombardy Region takes also part in other interregional networks.

On September 9, 1988, together with the regions Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes (France), Baden-Württemberg (Germany), Catalonia (Spain), Lombardy signed a cooperation agreement constituting

the network of the “Four Motors for Europe”. The goals of collaboration in 1988 were primarily related to economics and research as well as to art and culture. In the course of the following decades the scope and intensity of cooperation grew notably.

Within the remit of TRANSFORM, Lombardy Region has a third party, Azienda Regionale per l'Innovazione e gli Acquisti - ARIA which is a private entity created and owned by LR to manage the activities in governance-by-data, digital transformation, and public procurements.

Finanziaria per lo Sviluppo della Lombardia - Finlombarda SpA

Finlombarda – Finanziaria per lo Sviluppo della Lombardia S.p.A. - is a financial company fully-owned by Regione Lombardia. The company is in charge of structuring and implementing innovative financial initiatives of public finance on behalf of the Region, through the deployment of regional and EU resources as well as through its own resources. Finlombarda S.p.A. promotes competitiveness, growth, innovation, co-operation and internationalization of Lombardy’s entrepreneurship through regional and European fund management, business services (Enterprise Europe Network services) and territorial development support.

Finlombarda acts as main advisor of Lombardy Region for setting-up regional Research, Innovation and Competitiveness policies.

Thus, from 2012, Finlombarda supports the main DGs (DG Universities, Research and Open Innovation and DG Economic Development) to design, implement and update strategic regional programmes and plan such as the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) and the regional Three Years’ Strategic Programme for Research, Innovation and Technological Transfer, taking into account the specific territorial peculiarities. In particular, Finlombarda has supported Lombardy Region to involve territorial stakeholders during the S3 design and implementation phase. The complex dialogue was supported by a new and inclusive tool, the collaborative platform called “Open Innovation”.

2.2 Catalan cluster members profiles

Science for Change (SfC), the Catalan platform for citizen science, the cluster leader:

Science for Change is a SME born from the will to tackle societal and environmental challenges affecting communities using innovative solutions. SfC specializes in developing user-centered, innovative services and products based on citizen science, participatory strategies, community engagement and co-creation processes to facilitate social innovation. It uses a methodology based on a quadruple helix model of stakeholder engagement, to promote dialogue, increase transparency, and to co-design innovative solutions that are relevant to all the stakeholders involved. The identified

stakeholders are involved in every step of the process: from the co-design of the research question, to the definition and the data gathering strategy, to its validation, analysis and co-design of solutions. SfC empower communities using a bottom-up approach to co-design local solutions while promoting the participation of citizens in decision-making processes that affect their quality of life.

SfC has been created for the exploitation of results of the EU H2020 project D-NOSES (Distributed Network for Odour Sensing, Empowerment and Sustainability) with the aim of replicating the innovative methodology developed to co-design alternative solutions to odour pollution using citizen science and co-creation methodologies and a bottom-up approach. SfC will apply this methodology to other environmental issues putting citizens at the forefront always involving a quadruple helix model for increasing transparency and sustainability. SfC aligns its innovative products and services with the SDGs of the UN 2030 Agenda. Furthermore, it prioritizes to follow Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) dimensions.

Role: SfC is the leader of the Catalan cluster (WP4. Citizen Science in RIS3 - Catalonia Region). One of its functions is to coordinate the different activities of the cluster (Think Tank and pilot projects), guaranteeing cooperation and information between the different members of the cluster and leading the execution of the activities and their contents. In this aspect, it is also in charge of leading the dissemination and communication of the project's activities and outputs, mobilizing the other members of the cluster and other possible agents that work as multipliers (members of the Think Tank, among others). On the other hand, SfC also manages the coordination of the Catalan cluster with the rest of the project's clusters, with the aim of aligning the evolution of all the clusters in their territorial activities and above all in those activities that imply a global perspective of inter-cluster work (fundamentally WP2. Framework definition, oversight and shared learning, and WP7. Monitoring and Evaluation). SfC also leads the task 2.2 MAP.

The General Directorate of Economic Promotion and Regulation (GDPECR). Policy maker

The General Directorate of Economic Promotion and Regulation (GDPECR) is the unit in the Catalan Government responsible for the coordination and the monitoring of Catalonia's Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3CAT).

Within this framework of action, we work on integration RRI dimensions (Anticipation, Reflexivity, Inclusion and Responsiveness) in RIS3CAT through:

- The entrepreneurial discovery process: bottom-up approaches in which government, companies, the universities, research and innovation players and civil society (hereafter referred to quadruple-helix players) identify areas of specialisation in the territory and then design and implement programmes, actions and projects to promote them.

- Shared agendas for sustainability and social change: to articulate the collective action of various stakeholders aimed at addressing a common complex challenge and the problems that this challenge may generate. Shared agendas are articulated in three steps:
 - Understand systemic challenges and prepare the basis for collective action.
 - Co-design, test and disseminate new solutions to the problems identified through multi-stakeholder transformative-shared agendas.
 - Reproduce and amplify the solutions tested to transform the system.

In the new programming period (2021-2027), the aim of GDPECR is to go a step further by integrating the RRI dimensions in the RIS3CAT, with a strong focus on:

- Developing and testing methodologies and tools designed to enhance the participation of quadruple-helix players, especially the participation of civil society, to promote “R&I with society and for society”.
- Generating new narratives, frameworks and monitoring tools for RRI.

TRANSFORM is a crucial project for the GDPECR in order to better experiment, understand and apply citizen science to public policies.

The role that the GDPECR plays within the Catalan cluster and in the global TRANSFORM project is summarized as:

- To guide and facilitate the project framework so that the objectives are aligned with those of the Catalan ecosystem and its governance (That is achieved by connecting stakeholders, proposing relevant trends and actively involving in development).
- To be inspired by the evolution of the results of the local Cluster project to influence the RIS3CAT and adapt visions and public policies (this is done by involving, training and connecting decisive stakeholders of the public administration, academia and relevant companies).
- To learn with and from other regional clusters of Transform.

Opensystems, the research group expert in citizen science

OpenSystems is a multidisciplinary group founded in 2012 of the University of Barcelona (UB) that focuses on public participation as a core element of the way of doing science. The group is a leading research group in Spain, Catalonia and Barcelona contexts on the emerging field of Citizen Science. The group also belongs to the Universitat de Barcelona Institute of Complex Systems (UBICS) and the Complexity Lab Barcelona. OpenSystems works together with many actors and builds tailored-made research collectives to address concerns mostly grounded in urban contexts. The group has expertise in co-creating citizen science projects, in the subsequent data gathering, data interpretation and data

analysis processes especially when it includes human behaviour and social issues. Citizen science main issues of UB lie within the so-called citizen social science and within the scopes of data science, complex systems science and social science.

Role: Inside the Catalan cluster, UB contributes to the development of a citizen science project. More particularly, UB has been moderating one of the groups in the several workshops. In this context, UB has been contributing to the analysis of the citizen science practices inside the RRI framework. UB is also providing insights in the co-creation process. UB has also been focussed on the academics' perspective to bring citizen science in the Catalan Smart Specialization Strategy (S3). UB plans to have a key role in the design and development of the co-created citizen science pilot. UB also expects to deliver scientific results jointly with the rest of cluster partners (specially Science For Change) that provides evidence on the positive contribution. Once the pilot is launched, data analysis and data interpretation related to the specific challenge will also be delivered by UB and hopefully published in a scientific journal.

2.3 Brussels-Capital cluster members profiles

TRANSFORM regional cluster of Brussels-Capital counts three members:

BE participation, the Belgian platform for citizen participation, the cluster leader

Created in 2011, BE participation (BEpart) is a non-profit association based in Brussels. Grounded in a complex neighbourhood in one of the most populated areas of Brussels,

BEpart is the leader of WP2 Framework definition, oversight and shared learning. One of the tasks led by BEpart is T2.3 REFLECT, for which outcomes are gathered in this deliverable 2.3. BEpart is in charge of the general coordination of T2.3 for all clusters and more particularly of its implementation in the Brussels-Capital regional cluster. BEpart is also leader of WP5 Design for Social Innovation - Brussels-Capital Region, the WP dedicated to the activities carried out within the region cluster. BEpart representatives have extensive experiences of European project management, RRI processes including policy recommendations, coordination of participative processes in R&I and science engagement. BEpart is coordinating the work of the three members of the regional cluster planning all activities and the different phases of the social innovation process planned in WP5 (T5.1 to T5.5), engaging the regional public authority in charge of innovation in Brussels-Capital (Innoviris) and the academic partner, ELI-UCLouvain. BEpart is contributing to the design of the participative activities with its expertise in multistakeholder (quadruple helix) engagement including a strong knowledge and experience in citizen participation.

Innoviris, the regional RDI agency created by Brussels regional government

Innoviris - the Brussels Institute for Research and Innovation - is the regional RDI agency founded in 2003 by the Government of Brussels Capital Region. The agency implements the Brussels-Capital Region's RDI policy and offers funding to help universities, research centres, private companies, local authorities, public sector, and non-economic actors in developing new products and services. Key activities of Innoviris include to support scientific research and innovation. Innoviris funds scientific research and technological innovation. Businesses, universities, colleges, research centres, local authorities, public sector, and non-economic actors in the Brussels-Capital Region can apply for financial support for research and innovation projects on economic or non-economic purposes.

As regional administration in charge of innovation, Innoviris contributes to the regional RDI policymaking process (at the local, national, and European level) and works alongside with other RDI regional partners.

The participation of the Brussels Institute for Research and Innovation is directly linked to the core objective of the TRANSFORM project, namely to open up regional R&I activities to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation. The main objective of the project is to test and disseminate co-creation methodological frameworks for the implementation of Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3). Innoviris is the public organisation in charge of designing, implementing and financing the regional innovation programme and the S3. Their participation in the cluster activities ensures the participative process and innovation actions developed for the region are in lines with the R&I ecosystem and their priorities. The public authority in charge of R&I in the region will be directly involved in a transformative process and in pilot activities proposing to run R&I in a more participative way integrating more RRI elements. Their involvement in the WP5 activities has the aim to make them an active actor of the co-creation innovation process and to have an impact on regional R&I activities including S3. INNOVIRIS experience in running a number of co-created innovation programmes (e.g. cocreate - <https://innoviris.brussels/fr/co-creation>) and role in defining innovation programmes placed them as a key actor in the development of WP5 activities.

UCLouvain's 'Earth and Life Institute' (ELI-UCLouvain)

The 'Earth and Life Institute' (ELI) is one of the research institutes of the Université Catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain) in Belgium. It engages over 300 researchers, covering a broad spectrum of scientific disciplines related with earth and life sciences. Their common aim is to achieve a deeper understanding of the basic processes of the Earth & Life system at different scales and to design sustainable solutions addressing some of the major challenges of our societies. Thanks to the vast range of expertise involved, ELI is able to promote and implement multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches in the research projects it develops, and to stimulate interactions

between scientists with complementary skills. In particular, four leading economists within the institute focus on developing the original scientific methodologies needed for the modeling and assessment of socio-economic, environmental and health impacts of public policies and private strategies in a wide variety of fields (i.e. agricultural activities, agro-food industry, transport and mobility, extractive industry, recycling, water management, bio-economy and circular economy). Ignace Adant plays a leading role within the institute, focusing on research related to innovation within the field of circular economy and impact studies of private strategies and public policies. ELI-UCLouvain brings into the BCR cluster expertise and deep knowledge of the domain and methodology in which the participative activities of the region will be developed: Prof. Ignace Adant brings a proven track record in analysing radical innovations for the circular economy, within the private sector as well as supported by public regional and European funding into the project.

Expertise in Design Thinking applied to Innovations

ELI-UCLouvain focusses among other topics on technological, organizational and social innovation to support sustainable development and the transition to an economy based on renewable natural resources and biodiversity into cluster activities. ELI-UCLouvain will develop the application of Design Thinking to the various phases of the pilot activities foreseen in the Brussels cluster, guaranteeing a high level of viability, efficiency, legitimacy and, specifically, multi-stakeholder acceptability. ELI-UCLouvain takes the leads the application of the Design Thinking approach to the social innovation processes that are being chosen to be at the heart of the pilot activities of the Brussels Cluster of TRANSFORM.

3. Research and Innovation ecosystems in the TRANSFORM regions

In this chapter, the deliverable provides information on the research and innovation ecosystem of each region involved in the TRANSFORM project. This information was gathered as part of the mapping and collection of relevant data on regional R&I strategies.

3.1 Research and Innovation ecosystems in Lombardy

About TRANSFORM Lombardy cluster

In the realm of the TRANSFORM project the general commitment of the territorial ecosystem in Lombardy is to render more inclusive and transparent, ensuring that citizens' voices are heard and opinions taken into account, the setting up of key regional R&I strategies and actions, part of the S3 implementation.

In particular, the Lombardy Cluster implements a structured participatory agenda setting exercise (online - deploying the Open Innovation Platform)¹ to further open up the stakeholders and citizens engagement process in designing the next Three Years Strategic Plan Research, Innovation, and Technology Transfer - Piano Strategico Triennale (PST) (2021-2023), aiming at leading to an RRI oriented institutional change during the process.

The Lombardy cluster is supported by the scientific advice of Simon Burall (Involve), member of the TRANSFORM Advisory Board. The Lombardy cluster also takes advantage from the local Think Tank collaboration in performing a SWOT Analysis of RRI actions in the Region and co-creating indicators to analyze the RRI performance of Lombardy Region.

a) Main activities

- Participatory Research Agenda Setting in the design of the PST.
- Citizen Engagement in S3 (implementation).
- Regional RRI performance experimental evaluation.

b) Outputs

¹ In the Description of Action of the project the participatory activities have been planned as blended (online and offline). Due to the pandemic crisis, offline activities had to be avoided.

- Mutual learning exercises (online meetings) among Lombardy cluster partners in order to identify and map RRI activities of the Region and to plan how to introduce RRI-oriented institutional changes within LR.
- Embedding RRI into the objectives of the next S3 plan.
- Design and implementation of a capacity building exercise: organizing lectures and workshops on RRI and citizen engagement open to local R&I stakeholders and RL personnel not involved in TRANSFORM.
- Implementation of the LR Participatory agenda setting operational plan (including the refinement of the Open Innovation Platform interface to implement online citizen engagement tools) in order to conceive and conduct citizen engagement activities in the design of the next PST.
- Set-up a framework to conduct an RRI performance evaluation of LR actions.

c) To sum up

- In the next RL S3, RRI will be inserted as one of the objectives so that citizen engagement will be extensively applied in the implementation of S3. Stakeholder raising awareness and capacity building on RRI and citizen engagement have been planned to occur from now till the finalization of the S3 and beyond.
- Participatory research agenda setting will be performed to co-design regional PST that has to be accomplished by the first quarter of 2021.
- A series of digital refinements of the regional Open Innovation Platform for online participatory systems will also be achieved to foster engagement and usability.

Smart Specialisation Strategy – S3

LR developed its first S3 for the programming period 2014-2020². The Lombardy Strategy design phase was opened to specific regional stakeholder (e.g. Regional Technology Cluster, representatives of large companies, SMEs, etc.) and to online public consultation (surveys), but further consultations were then organized for the S3 updates. The 2014-2020 S3 has undergone an in itinere evaluation.

From April 2020 LR has started designing the new S3 (2021-2027). An internal working group dedicated to regional strategic programs on R&I and composed of regional Directorates and key regional stakeholders has been set up. LR is addressing the process thanks to a continuous dialogue with local stakeholders, the European Commission and other European regions involved in R&I international

² Lombardy Region (2014) [Research and Innovation Strategies for Research and Innovation in Lombardy – Executive Summary](#), Milan.

programs (Vanguard Initiative, S3 Thematic Platforms, etc.). Furthermore, an open stakeholder consultation was also launched and hosted on the regional Open Innovation Platform last Summer.

In line with the TRANSFORM activities, the goal is to embed RRI (including citizen engagement practices) into the objectives of the new S3, so to prepare the ground for the engagement of citizens in the S3 implementation phase.

Three Years Strategic Plan Research, Innovation, and Technology Transfer (PST)

According to the Regional Law no. 29/2016, the PST provides the framework for the governance of research and innovation at regional level and represents one of the key instruments for S3 implementation.

Its aims are:

- to identify and assess regional needs, trends and key priorities in terms of Research and Innovation.
- to plan a comprehensive set of actions to be put into practice over three years; to estimate the resources that are needed. And

to define potential impacts and results of the Plan.

The first PST (2018-2020) has mobilized up to 750 million Euros for research projects and was drafted also thanks to a thorough exchange of views with local stakeholders and innovation experts and professionals. Furthermore, an online public survey to comment, refine and improve the draft of the PST was hosted on the regional platform Open Innovation. The survey has received approximately 1,500 comments and detailed feedback. At the end of the process, the first PST has been outlined revolving around 8 regional ecosystems, which are considered key topics for the Region since addressing local needs. The 8 regional ecosystems almost overlap the 7 smart specialization areas depicted in the Lombardy Region S3 (2014-2020), which are:

- Aerospace;
- Agri-food;
- Eco-industry;
- Creative and cultural industries;
- Health industry;
- Advanced manufacturing;
- Sustainable mobility.

Smart Cities and Communities is also identified by Lombardy Region as a key driver to foster Emerging Industries.

There are also five major development areas identified by the Strategic Plan: technology transfer; development of human capital; use of frontier Internet of Things (IoT) and Information Communication Technology (ICT) to transform Lombardy into a 'smart' territory; personalized medicine; advanced agriculture and agri-food chain.

In order to align the regional 2018-2020 strategy to the principles and practice of RRI, the Regional Forum for Research and Innovation has also provided its input and suggestions for the PST.

In designing the next Strategic Plan, Lombardy Region will aim at opening up the process, drafting the plan according to local “missions” and fully aligning the PST to regional S3 priorities.

Responsible R&I governance and tools: Regional Forum for Research and Innovation and Open Innovation Platform

By Regional Law no. 29/2016, LR introduced both a new form of regional innovation governance and related strategic support tools into the regional system of research and innovation.

In this realm, the RRI approach plays a key role. In fact, RRI has been enshrined in the Law (article 3) as one of the funding principles and several activities have been foreseen to accomplish the goal of spreading the culture and the implementation of RRI.

[A Regional Forum for Research and Innovation](#) was established to advise on the responsible governance of regional research and innovation. The Forum is an independent body composed by ten international experts on science and society related issues (i.e. RRI, Technology Assessment, Public Engagement, Open Innovation, Open Data, Social Innovation and Bio- and Data-Ethics) and is serving from 2018 to 2020. The Forum is providing advice and proposing initiatives, anticipating the emerging needs of society to develop timely responses, and reflecting on and developing new strategies to engage citizens in planning and implementing research and innovation at regional level. From March 2020 onwards the Forum focused its action primarily on supporting the regional decision-maker on RRI practices for the management of the COVID-19 crisis and the subsequent recovery phase from a pandemic wave. FGB coordinated the drafting of the document "Forum's Flash recommendations on COVID-19 emergency", which incorporates a series of suggestions for the governance of key issues that emerged with the pandemic crisis.

Furthermore, in the last years Lombardy Region has developed and refined a new instrument of contact and dialogue with research and innovation stakeholders and the public, the [Open Innovation Platform](#). The Platform has been built around the key principles of Quadruple Helix Open Innovation model and is a virtual space where the Regional Government, industrial players, academia

representatives and societal actors work jointly. Currently, the platform has more than 7,000 active participants and various consultancy calls have been hosted within this tool. In this broad process of rethinking and restructuring regional Research and Innovation areas, a continuous dialogue with local researchers who can support the Region through the delivery of scientific data and evidence has been pursued and will be enhanced in order to produce useful and effective policies to address citizens' needs.

3.2 Research and Innovation ecosystems in Catalonia

a. Activities so far

From the beginning of the project, the catalan cluster have been holding regular meetings led by Science for Change (through digital means due to the COVID crisis) with the objectives of carrying out a prior evaluation of the catalan R&I ecosystem and defining different possibilities to embed RRI in RIS3CAT. A process of intra and intercluster mutual learning and reflection has been developed, which has resulted in the following activities:

THINK TANK: A reflection process between the catalan cluster members at one level, and across the three regional clusters at another level was carried out to define the role of local Think Tanks. Being aligned with the common needs and expectations shared by the different clusters but also taking into account the specificities of the catalan ecosystem, the Think Tank in Catalonia was launched in June 2020 (Over 55 members form 3H organizations of the R&I ecosystem), with a strong first effort in 1) reflection on the potential of RRI and citizen science to improve R&I and 2) capacity building to foster RRI and citizen science in the region. The rest of the objectives will be developed from 2021 onwards (see deliverable 2.1).

PRIOR EVALUATION OF R&I CATALAN ECOSYSTEM. The R&I regional ecosystems are highly complex and disperse realities which involve a wide range of organizations and public administration programmes and strategies. A deeper mapping of the R&I regional ecosystems will be carried out in Task 2.2 MAP, but a prior evaluation of its most important elements was needed to better define pilot projects and TRANSFORM activities. Therefore, a prior evaluation has been developed within the cluster to better understand the RIS3CAT planning and implementation (meaning it's instruments, funding programmes, projects and implementing organizations) as well as its policy, societal and economic context. The aim was to have a general picture of the integration of RRI elements into the R&I ecosystem and capture the needs and possibilities to perform TRANSFORM activities to have the widest impact. The results of the evaluation are integrated in chapter 5 below, in this deliverable. The main conclusion is that with few exceptions RRI is not integrated explicitly in the main instruments to support R&I in Catalonia. RRI specific agendas do have more importance, specifically public participation which is part of the core objectives of some different RIS3CAT instruments and is also mentioned at least in some public funding programmes. The main discussion here is about the

“quality” of the participation procedures. On the other hand, RRI has entered in the last years in the Catalan R&I ecosystem at implementation level, taking advantage of European funding programmes: many relevant actors of the Catalan R&I ecosystem, including the Catalan Government, are working on RRI projects (and also projects that highlight some of the RRI specific agendas).

[SeeRRI](#) and TRANSFORM: The General Directorate for Economic Promotion, Competition and Regulation is a partner with the aim of exploring how to integrate RRI and citizen science in the RIS3CAT 2021-2027.

AGAUR (The Agency for Management of University and Research Grants) participates in the [GRACE](#) project (Grounding RRI Actions to Achieve Institutional Changes in European Research Funding and Performing Organisations); it's working on the implementation of a set of RRI-oriented Grounding Actions (GAs) aimed at achieving institutional change to favour gender equality, ethics and integrity and open access in its research funding schemes and processes. The GAs will result in a set of clearly identifiable institutional arrangements, with the development of a tailored 8-year RRI Roadmap that will be sustainable over time which aims: i) to implement changes to embed RRI in the current institutional practices and funding programmes; ii) to promote processes of institutional change as a multiplier agent of R&I policies and principles for the whole Catalan ecosystem; and iii) to provide guidance and share best practices on institutional changes towards gender, ethics and open access to other organisations.

GDPECR is collaborating with AGAUR and will collaborate with other units in Government to define guidelines about how to integrate RRI dimensions in the RIS3CAT calls. GDPECR is also collaborating with AGAUR to define relevant RRI indicators for the RIS3CAT.

Probably the field more advanced in RRI is health. The Catalan Agency for Health Quality and Evaluation (AQuAS) publishes the [SARIS monographs](#), reports aimed at decision-makers, professionals and non-specialized audiences with the aim of analyzing current issues around health research that stimulate and encourage reflection. The collection includes a series on responsible research addressing the interaction of research with society. It has also integrated the [gender and citizen participation agendas](#) within its evaluation procedures of the research and innovation projects funded with PERIS.

Instead of being powerful, these examples show that some institutions are willing to deepen in RRI and explore its potential but it doesn't mean that RRI is widely integrated across all programmes nor internally within the institutions.

b) Planned activities:

THINK TANK: the members of the Think Tank (that have been devoted to capacity building) are planned to be reconducted to other Think TANK objectives, mainly the contribution to the evaluation

of the RRI & public participation performance in the R&I ecosystem in Catalonia and the impact of TRANSFORM activities.

Pilot projects on citizen science: the participatory approach to be developed by the catalan cluster is citizen science. Citizen science is, by definition, a methodology that can be applied at implementation level but, as the activities carried out so far have shown, there is a high opportunity of embedding citizen science processes and results in public policies, both in designing more efficient policies tackling societal challenges and also contributing to its monitorization. The aim of the catalan cluster is to develop pilot projects that demonstrate this potentiality covering the whole process. That's why the preliminary perspective for pilot projects is to devote them to the Circular Economy and Waste Management sector in the B-30 area, regarding that different funding programmes and local strategies are being launched with the aim of improving municipal waste collection to comply with european objectives. There is a strong conviction that a deeper citizen participation is needed to achieve this goal. However, during the capacity building sessions, other areas have emerged as highly interested in applying citizen science to the (1) gender dimension of health issues and 2) environmental quality). Currently, the catalan cluster is reflecting on how to readapt the original plan to give coverage to the emerging needs.

Smart Specialisation Strategy – current S3 and renewal process

RIS3 2014-2020

For the 2014-2020 period, the European Union called on all regions to draw up and implement regional innovation strategies for smart specialisation (RIS3 strategies), co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). The objective of RIS3 strategies is to focus the economic and knowledge specialisation of regions (based on their resources, strengths and capabilities) and to promote action plans providing public support for innovation to strengthen the competitiveness of the territory and foster more sustainable and inclusive growth.

RIS3 strategies are based on open innovation models in which, besides companies, research and innovation actors and governments, citizens must also be present, as they are the main beneficiaries and users of innovations. This is particularly important in a context in which new responses to the great economic, social and environmental challenges necessarily entail changes in behaviour at both individual and societal scale.

The RIS3 strategy for Catalonia (RIS3CAT) was approved in 2014. The RIS3CAT Action Plan has a budget of more than 400 million euros from the ERDF to promote innovation in the sectors defined as priorities in Catalonia. This sum is used to cofinance projects and investments worth more than 1,000 million euros in total.

RIS3CAT has four strategic objectives:

1. To enhance the competitiveness of the business fabric by improving the efficiency of production processes, promoting internationalisation and reorienting established sectors towards activities with greater added value.
2. To promote new emerging economic activities through research, creativity and innovation in order to create and exploit new market niches.
3. To consolidate Catalonia as a European knowledge hub and connect the country's technological and creative capabilities with both sectors that already exist in the territory and those that may emerge.
4. To make global improvements to the Catalan system of innovation, improving the competitiveness of companies, particularly SMEs, and orienting public policies towards the promotion of innovation, internationalisation and entrepreneurship.

RIS3CAT focuses on seven sectoral areas of specialisation and facilitating technologies that will help Catalonia to make the transition to a more competitive, sustainable and inclusive economic model.

- Food
- Energy and resources
- Industrial systems
- Design-based industries
- Industries related to sustainable mobility
- Health Industries
- Cultural and experience-based industries

Figure 1. RIS3CAT' seven sectoral areas

RIS3CAT combines traditional instruments for supporting research and innovation with more innovative mechanisms aimed at promoting new forms of cooperation between people and organisations to co-create public policies and innovative solutions that will enable the formulation of effective responses to the great challenges that face our society.

The main innovative instruments are:

- RIS3CAT communities: Sectoral groups of companies and R&D&I stakeholders, which develop common sector-based research and innovation agendas and implement collaborative projects..
- PECT: Innovative projects promoted by local authorities in cooperation with research and innovation players and other actors in the territory with a view to responding to challenges of a territorial nature. These PECT are evolving towards shared R&I agendas towards sustainability and social change.
- The Catlabs program supports collaborative open social innovation and focuses on methodological aspects: what role should labs (fablabs, living labs or others) play in the new paradigm of open science and innovation? And in addressing social challenges?
- Public procurement of innovation (PPI) to develop and implement new solutions to societal challenges through the acquisition of new processes or services.
- Design and comparison of new processes and methodologies aimed at responding to complex social challenges that require a collective impact approach and the involvement of quadruple helix stakeholders (shared agendas, SeRRI project, TRANSFORM).
- Development and implementation of monitoring and evaluation systems that focus on collective learning (as well as accountability) and on impact on complex and dynamic environments.

These new tools, the fruit of a new paradigm and a new way of understanding research and innovation (more responsible, more open, more collaborative, more transversal, etc.), often clash with the contradictions of an old paradigm that is still too present among the different quadruple helix actors. This old paradigm greatly hinders the possibility of sharing knowledge and generating methodological or procedural innovations without arousing suspicion. The contradictions between the new tools and the dominant paradigm are manifested in different areas: in regulations that restrict the implementation of projects; in the way of working; in the way of understanding collaboration; in closed-minded views about opportunities to create shared value, etc.

- More information about the current S3 in Catalonia is available on the S3 platform: <http://catalunya2020.gencat.cat/en/inici/>

Some lessons learned

- New methodologies, approaches and skills are needed to better understand and address together with 4H actors societal challenges (SDGs) in more effective ways.
- Public administrations and European funds are key to articulate more effective answers to societal challenges. Public administrations need more skills and tools to understand and address systemic challenges (with all their complexity) and mechanisms to work with 4H players in the design and the implementation of innovative transformative actions.
- S3, through EDP, can become a key instrument to accelerate the transition of the territories towards more sustainable and inclusive pathways (circular economy, I4.0, etc.) through the alignment of multiple actors, funds and programs.

b) Update on the development of the new S3 plan for the period 2021-2027

The COVID-19 crisis poses key questions as to what lessons will be learnt and, above all, what will need to change in order to promote sustainable and inclusive development pathways aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

RIS3CAT 2021-2027 will be challenge oriented, which means that it will be a transformative research and innovation agenda, the main objective of which is to mobilise the efforts of the Catalan research and innovation ecosystem to respond to the major social and environmental challenges that face the region. Meeting these challenges, which are set out in the 2030 Agenda, requires in-depth discussions about transformations at three levels: the economic system, social relations and the relationship between people and the natural environment.

Conceptually, RIS3CAT 2021-2027 is inspired by the theoretical framework of [transformative innovation policy](#), promoted by the [Transformative Innovation Policy Consortium](#) (hereafter, TIPC), by the need for [responsible research and innovation](#), and by the concept of [shared value](#) proposed by Porter and Kramer.

Regarding RRI, RIS3CAT 2021-2027 aims to integrate the four dimensions of the responsible research and innovation (RRI) approach proposed by Stilgoe et al.³ into smart specialisation processes (following Fitjar et al.)⁴, meaning Anticipation, Reflexivity, Inclusion, Responsiveness.

³ Stilgoe, J., Owen, R., & Macnaghten, P. (2013). Developing a framework for responsible innovation. *Research Policy*, 42(9), 1568-1580. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2013.05.008>

⁴ Fitjar, R. D., Benneworth, P., & Asheim, B. T. (2019). Towards regional responsible research and innovation? Integrating RRI and RIS3 in European innovation policy. *Science and Public Policy*, 46(5), 772–783. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scz029>

According to this, efforts to promote innovation should focus, not on optimisation, but on transformation. Public research and innovation policies should promote transformations that can generate radical new alternatives to current practices and systems. Although these alternatives may not be seen as feasible in the short term, sustained investment in transformative niches such as, for example, occurred in solar and wind power in the past, can lead the way towards new, more sustainable and inclusive practices that transform unsustainable current systems.

Policy experimentation lies at the heart of transformative innovation policy and should be a key element for the next RIS3CAT: it enables the creation and testing of alternative practices that can enter into competition with prevailing practices and generate new capacities and processes so that these new practices can replace the former ones. Experimentation enables actors in a territory (government, academia, business and civil society) to collectively determine which public policies, which technologies and which processes are best suited to providing just, sustainable responses to shared challenges. It is important, then, to ensure that transformative innovation policy promotes the creation of spaces for experimentation.

There is a proposal to create a new EDP program with technical offices (integrated in the Administration and in the RIS3CAT governance system) structured by challenges to dynamise and coordinate the EDP with 4H players. The challenge-oriented priorities are the following:

- The transition to a green, carbon-neutral economy.
- The transition of industry towards digitalisation.
- The transition to a universal and sustainable health system that is both resilient and adaptive.
- The generation of new shared business models.
- Improving mobility and connectivity.

Territorial rebalancing through the support to transformative shared agendas to accelerate industrial transition, the transition of rural areas to the bioeconomy and the digitalisation (smart cities and smart territories).

RIS3CAT 2021-2027 will aim to address the major structural challenges that face our society through a methodology based on [shared agendas](#). This is an innovative methodology, based on various experimental projects for shared agendas articulated from the bottom up with the participation of the Catalan Government, local authorities, universities and other players in the region, and in cooperation with other European regions and experts from the TIPC and the European Commission's Joint Research Centre.

In RIS3CAT 2021-2027 the governance system and the entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP) will be designed in order to encourage anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness.

The EDP, the shared agendas and the 4H players collaboration to address common challenges require the support of digital tools.

- The [RIS3MCAT](#): digital platform that integrates, relates and makes interoperable the results of science and innovation projects funded by European funds and relate them to SDG's

Figure 2. RIS3CAT digital platform

Source: <http://ris3mcat.gencat.cat>

- [Participa.gencat](#): is a participatory digital platform to facilitate and foster citizens (and other stakeholders) participation in policy-making specifically in the context of public consultations.
- A new platform is being developed for challenges related to SDGs and on a searcher to map and connect the challenges and the networks of actors.

c. Main milestones of S3 development in 2020:

In 2020 the work has focused on extracting the main learnings from the period 2014-2020 ([lessons learned from the RIS3CAT 2014-2020](#)) in collaboration with stakeholders, in the framework of the RIS3CAT monitoring dynamics.

The revision of the RIS3CAT for the next period will take into account these learnings and will integrate the regional priorities defined through participatory processes in the diverse regional plans and strategies approved by the Government ([Catalonia's Economic Reactivation and Social Protection Plan](#),

[National Pact for a knowledge-based society](#)) or in elaboration (for example Catalonia's roadmap for a circular economy, or Catalonia's bioeconomy strategy).

The main changes in the RIS3CAT are 1) the reorientation from sectors and technologies towards challenges, and 2) the creation of an Entrepreneurial Opportunity Discovery Programme to articulate the participation of quadruple-helix players in the governance of RIS3CAT, the identification of challenges and opportunities, the definition of priorities and the design, implementation and monitoring of research and innovation instruments and projects. This is aimed at accelerating the transition towards more sustainable and inclusive pathways.

The specific objectives of the Programme will be:

- To explore and identify, with quadruple-helix players, opportunities, challenges, obstacles and needs in order to define and prioritise actions that promote the industrial transition towards more sustainable and inclusive development patterns.
- To channel the participation of quadruple-helix players in the governance of RIS3CAT and in monitoring actions.
- To explore and identify, with quadruple-helix players, entrepreneurial opportunities that generate shared value (economic, social, environmental) and articulate tools and actions to implement them.
- To promote international cooperation and participation in transnational networks.

The revision of the RIS3CAT and the RIS3CAT Action Plan 2021-2027 will be approved in 2021.

3.3 Research and Innovation ecosystems in Brussels-Capital

a. Activities so far

From the beginning of the project in January 2020, the Brussels-Capital region cluster led by BE participation has applied co-creation principles to define the action plan of the regional activities including regular exchanges, capacity building activities, mapping and reflections. Despite the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdown, partners have continued to hold weekly online meetings without interruption. Here is a summary of the activities organised so far:

THINK TANK – A reflection process between the Brussels cluster members at one level, and across the three regional clusters at another level was carried out to define the role of local Think Tanks. Based on the needs and expectations raised in each region, the plan is to form Think Tanks that will support the definition of an evaluation strategy to assess the social impacts of TRANSFORM pilot activities. At Brussels-Capital Region level, the discussions came to the conclusions that Think Tanks members

should be identified for their experience and skills on the assessment of R&I activities looking at the impact on the local public good.

OVERVIEW - An overview of Research and innovation funding programs in the Brussels-Capital region is available chapter 5 below, in this deliverable. The aim here was to have a clear picture of the integration of RRI elements into R&I programmes in the region. The mapping exercise highlighted the fact that a number of RRI dimensions like the citizen engagement, the ethics considerations, the gender equality and the link with STEM education are present in existing programmes but are not widely integrated across all programmes. The main funding programmes of INNOVIRIS clearly integrating RRI elements identified are:

- Co-create – Since 2015 Innoviris has supported, through the Co-Creation action, the exploration, experimentation and production of co-created knowledge for urban resilience. <https://www.cocreate.brussels/>
- Test it: Through the Test it action, Innoviris wishes to enable innovators to develop, experiment and test their products, solutions, concepts with end users. This action targets applied R&I projects carried out within living labs involving researchers, users and a user platform.
- Former programme ANTICIPATE: "Anticipate" research projects questioned the urban complexity of Brussels and aimed to exploit the results of research for the benefit of society.

REFLECT – A reflection process with the cluster members exploring the broad topic of circular economy, the cluster selected specific community needs and challenges to address. The activities implemented so far are a SWOT analysis held on 21 February 2020 and a reflection exercise using collaborative tools on the R&I ecosystem of the Brussels-Capital region and the circular economy.

This co-creation process conducted among the cluster members enabled them to further develop the initial plan described in TRANSFORM's project Description of action, WP5 Design for Social Innovation – Brussels-Capital Region. The mapping exercise highlighted the need to not only build a pilot action to constitute a best practice on the integration of RRI in S3 (INSPIRE) but also to accompany existing programmes not currently applying RRI dimensions (INSTILL). More information about this below.

b. Participatory approach used in the cluster

For its pilot activities, the Brussels-Capital Region cluster will carry out a process of design thinking for social innovation focused on circular economy. The design thinking methodology enables the cluster to better understand the regional context and to implement research and observation methodologies ensuring a deep understanding of user needs and engagement of the local community. Beside one core pilot activity, the Brussels-Capital Region will also focus on capacity building towards strengthening core RRI elements in the implementation of S3 strategies within the context of R&I.

c. Update on the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) in Brussels-Capital Region

S3 priorities of the region 2016-2020

The three priorities of the current Smart Specialisation Strategy in Brussels-Capital Region are:

- Health - personalised medicine and well-being: personalized medicine and care, improving the hospital's care chain (e-health), prevention (improving environmental and nutritional quality).
- Environment - green economy: energy efficiency, sustainable chemistry, circular economy, mobility.
- ICT - digital economy: big data, IoT, information security, image processing.

In addition, the current S3 includes four transversal objectives:

- improving innovation chain,
- new forms of innovation and new R&D&I actors
- Communication and awareness about RDI
- Broad, participatory and efficient governance of the PRI (Plan Régional d'Innovation).

Figure 3. Priorities and objective of Brussels-Capital Region Smart Specialisation Strategy 2016-2020

The three local priorities are described in detail in the Regional Innovation Plan (PRI), developed by Innoviris and renovated every 3 years.

The TRANSFORM cluster for Brussels-Capital region will focus on one key priority of Brussels Region's territorial development: Green economy, and more particularly, social innovations in Circular Economy.

- More information about the current S3 in Brussels-Capital is available on the S3 platform: <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/regions/BE1/tags/BE1>

- More information about the Regional Innovation Plan 2016-2020: <https://innoviris.brussels/regional-innovation-plan>

Update on the development of the new S3 plan for the period 2021-2025

Nelawu Malanda, policy-advisor and representative of Innoviris in the TRANSFORM project presented the Smart Specialisation Strategy and innovation plan of Brussels-Capital region for 2021-2025 during the last project meeting on 28 September 2020.

To formulate the new S3, Innoviris built a steering Committee formed of various stakeholders and organisations representing different sectors (construction, finance, universities, environment, statistics). Partners involved can be seen in the Figure below.

Figure 4. Regional Innovation Plan and S3 2021-2025 - Steering Committee members

The methodology (see Figure 4) used for the renewal of the S3 consisted in:

- Defining societal challenges,
- Mapping Research, Development and Innovation ecosystem The Entrepreneurial Discovery Process (EDP) was used in that context.

These two processes led to a map of Strategic Innovation Domains to prioritize. The purpose was to build a flexible and agile S3, having the capacity to transform the current sectors, taking into account the bottom-up needs as well as the top-down priorities.

Figure 5 – Methodology – renewal of the S3 and creation of the Regional Innovation Plan 2021-2025

The strategy took into account global trends including the Sustainable Development Goals, the Green Deal and Horizon Europe - mission areas.

The societal challenges that have been highlighted by this process are:

- Climate and Energy: reduction of emissions from mobility, construction, industry; biodiversity; energy efficiency of buildings and enterprises; renewable energy and smart grids.
- Resources optimisation: Circular Economy, e-waste management, eco-design, industrial symbiose, economy of functionality; BeinT (digitalisation of enterprises - small and medium)
- Inclusive and representative society: addressing social inequalities; social and cooperative economy and innovation; addressing the digital gap focussing on e-inclusion; inclusive public space and homing; participative and representative governance.
- Health & well-being: personalised health care; med/lifetech, e-health; more sophisticated diagnostics and therapies; new organisation of care; epidemics management.
- Healthy Food for all: sustainable, healthy and safe food systems; ecological and circular urban agriculture; healthy and sustainable alternative food products
- Mobility: new form and systems of urban transport; modal shift and mobility-as-a-service; focus on urban logistic and distribution.

Altogether, these societal challenges and their accompanying strategies aim to define the future economy of the Brussels-Capital region that should be competitive with productive capacity; digital; sustainable, resilient and inclusive.

To build the EDP, several activities are currently implemented, including the work with the Steering Committee and a survey that was launched recently (see: shorturl.at/egGHL).

Main milestones of S3 development in 2020:

- September: Survey

- October: International Benchmarking
- October: Refine Ecosystem and Innovation Camp
- November: Policy Mix
- December: Final Report (roadmap)

4. Results of the SWOT analysis

4.1 Objectives

The objectives of the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats analysis carried out in the three regional clusters of the TRANSFORM project were:

- To identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that the cluster (internal factors) could encounter to achieve the overall objective of the project taking into account the specific framework of the regional context (external factors).
- Evaluate any weaknesses and risks upstream in order to develop strategies and anticipate.
- Reflect on these aspects within the cluster and identify the skills that can strengthen the partnership.
- Reflect on the different directional possibilities of the project within the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework.

4.2 Guidelines

SWOT analysis (Strengths - Weaknesses - Opportunities - Threats) is a strategy analysis tool. It combines the study of the strengths and weaknesses of an organisation, a geographical area, or a sector (internal factors), with the study of the opportunities and threats to their environment (external factors). It is instrumental in development strategy formulation⁵.

	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
Internal factors	Strengths	Weaknesses
External factors	Opportunities	Threats

Table 1. Rationale of SWOT analysis

⁵ European Union – Capacity4dev, Evaluation Unit DEVCO, Evaluation methodological approach, SWOT (Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats), Last update 15 November 2020, Retrieved from Internet on 14 October 2020 from: https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/evaluation_guidelines/wiki/swot-strengths-weakness-opportunities-threats-0

4.2.1 Objectives of the SWOT analysis in TRANSFORM:

The objectives of the SWOT analysis to be ran in the context of the TRANSFORM project, WP2 Framework definition, oversight and shared learning, Task 2.3 REFLECT are:

- To identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that the cluster (internal factors) could encounter to achieve the overall objective of the project taking into account the specific framework of the regional context (external factors).
- Evaluate any weaknesses and risks upstream in order to develop strategies and anticipate.
- Reflect on these aspects within the cluster and identify the skills that can strengthen the partnership.
- Reflect on the different directional possibilities of the project within the Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework.

4.2.2 Implementation of the analysis:

The cluster leaders were expected to facilitate the process and contribute to the exercise, making sure the collaborative session contributed to the strategy of the cluster, remained in the project framework and contributed to the general objectives.

4.2.3 The steps involved in a SWOT analysis:

1. Setting the preconditions of the SWOT analysis mainly consisted in the selection of the participants. In the case of TRANSFORM it included the:

- a. clusters members mainly for internal factors but also for external factors and
- b. possibly the Think Tank members or a subset of this group to support the identification of external factors mainly but contribute to the analysis of the internal factors too. The aim was to involve the stakeholders and experts concerned with the strategy having experience and knowledge of the Research and Innovation ecosystem of the region.

For the selection of the participants, the organiser and facilitator ensured a balanced representation of different R&I stakeholder groups and expression of interests. The facilitator had the role to ensure a balanced influence of each stakeholder group during the SWOT analysis.

2. The level of analysis relates to the object of the analysis, e.g. a region, an ecosystem, a country, an organisation, etc... In the context of TRANSFORM, the focus is the cluster composition and strategy. The object of the internal analysis is the cluster (members and strategy of the pilot), while the object of the external analysis is the R&I ecosystem.

3. The preparation of the session consisted in the way each dimension of the SWOT analysis was studied. The analysis started with the internal factors and finished with the external ones:

- a. *Strengths*: identify positive internal factors that the cluster or at least one member of the cluster controls and that represents a basis for the next steps of the pilot. E.g. Motivation and engagement to link S3 and RRI among the members of the cluster.
- b. *Weaknesses*: They are the negative internal factors that the cluster or at least one member of the cluster can have an impact on and that require improvements and anticipative strategy. E.g. The cluster does not include a representative from the private sector.

To support the analysis of the internal factors, and counterbalance the possible bias and subjective elements, presentation of best practices was used to show what works or not in similar situations.

- c. *Opportunities*: list and analyse positive external factors the cluster can take advantage of in the region’s R&I ecosystem taking into account its strengths and weaknesses. The opportunities are mainly beyond the influence of the cluster members. E.g. After the Covid-19 crisis, the evolution of the society will result in an attitude more open to a change in the way R&I is operated with more participatory approaches.
- d. *Threats*: are the negative external factors or limitations the clusters should identify as possible barriers for the development of the pilot. E.g. Political and economic crisis due to the COVID-19 outbreak.

4. Combination of the SWOT components to develop a synthesis to take the most out of the analysis. The checklist proposed by European Union – Capacity4dev, Evaluation Unit DEVCO, in its Wiki Page ‘Evaluation methodological approach, SWOT’⁶ can be seen below:

			<i>Internal approach</i>		
			<i>List of the strength</i>	<i>List of the weak-nesses</i>	A study of the reasons why strengths overcome weak-nesses
			How can strengths be maximised?	How can weaknesses be minimised?	
External approach	<i>List of the opportu-nities</i>	How can opportuniti-es be maxi-mised?	How can strengths be used to take advantage of opportu-nities?	How can weaknesse-s be corrected to take advantage of opportu-nities?	
	<i>List of the threats</i>	How can threats be minimised ?	How can strengths be used to reduce threats?	How can weaknesse-s and threats be minimised?	
		A study of the reasons why opportunities minimise threats			

⁶ Idem

Table 2. Connection between SWOT's components

The SWOT analysis is a useful tool to identify and analyse opportunities and strengths (avoiding weaknesses and threats) that enabled the cluster to leverage a realistic plan. The SWOT analysis is the analysis that precedes the development of the strategy and the action plan of the cluster based on informed choices.

4.3 Lombardy Cluster

The objective of the SWOT analysis was to assess the internal and external factors conditioning the RRI actions and performance within the institutional setting of Lombardy Region. The SWOT analysis was carried out by selected members of Lombardy Cluster Think Tank (TT), together with the full Lombardy cluster during an online meeting held on October 26th, 2020. The group of TT Members have been selected according to their knowledge on RRI and on regional mechanisms and procedures. For the selection criteria and list of the whole TT please see deliverable TRANSFORM D2.1.

<p style="text-align: center;">STRENGTHS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutionalisation of RRI with the law "Lombardy is Research and Innovation" • Regional Forum for Research and Innovation • Willingness to listen from Lombardy Region around science and society issues (reflexivity) • RRI in some regional calls • Feasibility studies around science and society issues as engagement tool • Open databases • Engagement of schools (e.g. Premio Lombardia è Ricerca for students) • Lombardia Innovativa: mapping organisations that conduct co-creation activities with final users 	<p>Open Innovation Platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • very useful tool for stakeholders • need to increase accessibility for citizens <p>Capacity Building on RRI</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">WEAKNESSES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to include RRI terminology and criteria in the regional calls • Need to have specific budget for public communication in regional calls • Need to introduce open access policies • Need for a centralized budget for open access • Include civil society/science and society experts in the evaluation boards of calls and prizes • Ex post evaluations criteria
<p style="text-align: center;">OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RRI as a concrete and valuable opportunity for better products that are aligned to market needs • Strong RRI ecosystem within the regional framework to gather ideas, inspirations, best practices • RRI as a tool for research and innovation advancement/survival 		<p style="text-align: center;">THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not clear ideas on the differences between RRI, CSR/Social Innovation • Risk to exploit the contribution from citizens without rewarding them/ involving them in the following steps of the innovation process

Figure 6 - Think Tank Lombardy Cluster SWOT Analysis: Main Results

Source: FGB 2020

Description of results:

Strengths

The first group of strengths within the Lombardy regional framework is connected to the fact that LR is officially committed to RRI. First, the Regional Law no. 29/2016 mentions RRI as a principle underlying LR actions in the field of R&I. Second, LR introduced the Regional Forum for Research and Innovation, which is devoted to support the responsible governance of R&I in the region. Third, RRI is one of the founding principles also in the PST.

A further general strength is the ability of LR of being reflexive and willing to listen to the citizens' and stakeholders' voices and to open up the debate on R&I, through mechanisms and tools such as the so-called Open Innovation Platform.

The TT members identified also a quite long list of very concrete strengths that are directly connected to RRI actions or RRI dimensions:

- The presence of RRI in some regional R&I calls; furthermore, some regional calls for feasibility studies around science and society issues are de facto used as stakeholder engagement tools.
- The existence of open databases.
- The engagement of schools and students in regional prizes.
- The presence of initiatives to map R&I organizations that are implementing co-creation activities with end-users.

Weaknesses

A lot of issues identified as weaknesses have been turned into suggestions for actions.

List of suggestions for actions:

- Inclusion of RRI terminology and criteria in the regional R&I calls.
- Introduction of budget for public communication in the R&I regional calls, to encourage effective and professional communication strategies in research and innovation projects.
- Design and implementation of open access policies and a centralized budget for open access to make the R&I process more open and accessible.
- Involvement of civil society representatives in the evaluation of R&I proposals and also among the members of the juries of regional prizes.
- Adoption of ex-post evaluations mechanisms on already implemented activities to promote a reflection on how to improve RRI performance more concretely.

Opportunities

Two main groups can be distinguished:

- The first group of opportunities is connected to RRI in general, namely to the advantages of RRI adoption by industries and by research institutions in terms of aligning the products to the market needs and in terms of bringing research closer to the citizens.
- A specific opportunity for the Lombardy Region is identified in its strong RRI ecosystem, which can gather ideas, inspiring examples and best practices on RRI.

Risks

Two general risks have also been identified:

- There are no clear ideas among the regional industrial players about the differences between RRI, CSR, Social Innovation, and other innovation/business approaches.
- It is quite common that participatory processes exploit the contribution from citizens without rewarding them or involving them in the following steps of the innovation path, leaving them behind and losing key opportunities on the way.

Hybrid issues

Some further key cross-cutting considerations raised during the discussion are represented in yellow in the table.

First, the Open Innovation Platform, which is a virtual space where the Regional Government, Industrial players, academia representatives and other societal actors can dialogue on R&I issues has been described as a key strength of the Lombardy Region. At the same time, however, some refinements could be introduced to make this platform more accessible to the citizens. This suggestion is particularly relevant within the realm of TRANSFORM, as a refinement of the platform is foreseen also in the project proposal.

Second, RRI capacity-building activities have also been described during the meeting as both a weakness, due to the lack of this kind of actions at the moment, but also as an opportunity as they are now ongoing thanks to the TRANSFORM project.

The results of the SWOT analysis will contribute to the set of information at LR's disposal to shape the design and implementation of both the 2021-2027 S3 and 2021-2023 PST.

Moreover, the discussion highlighted how the actions to be implemented under TRANSFORM are in line with the RRI needs of the local TT members.

4.4 Catalan cluster

Experts involved in the SWOT analysis and information sources:

This SWOT analysis has been developed by the members of the Catalan cluster of TRANSFORM based in the following information sources:

- Documentation related to the RIS3CAT strategy.
- Results obtained during the 2 workshops carried out with the Catalan Think Tank members (approximately 60 members from organizations of the regional R&I ecosystem: academia, private sector and regional and local public administration).
- Data from the RIS3-MCAT, a platform that integrates, relates and makes interoperable the results of science and innovation projects funded by European funds.
- Professional experience of the Catalan cluster members (Science for Change, Opensystems and the General Directorate for Economic Promotion, Competition and Regulation).

Results of the SWOT analysis

STRENGTHS

- 13 organizations working on 12 projects related or including RRI funded by European funds (27.887.281€)
- Public administration leadership & experience in RRI and stakeholder engagement
- Leadership by the regional administration in charge of implementing RIS3CAT in promoting public and stakeholder engagement
- Quadruple helix stakeholder engagement is part of the objectives of the [RIS3CAT 2014-2020](#)
- Pilot innovative experiences on stakeholder engagement have been already implemented at regional administration level ([shared agendas for sustainability and social change](#), [Specialization and Territorial Competitiveness Projects \(PECTs\)](#), [RIS3CAT communities](#), [RIS3CAT monitoring](#))
- The regional administration has already participated in other European projects devoted to embedding RRI in RIS3 ([SeeRRI](#)) – also funded by SwafS-14
- Co-design and citizen participation are already part of the requirements of several public calls for proposals related to R&I (ex. [call for pilot projects for innovative public procurement in the field of selective collection of municipal waste](#))
- Academia leadership in citizen science

- There are more than 30 active citizen science initiatives led by Catalan universities, research centers and SMEs. Most Catalan universities have researchers with projects implementing citizen science practices.
- Barcelona municipality is committed in the promotion and development of citizen science through the Barcelona Citizen Science Office. It relies on organizing public and educational programs and in reinforcing the community of practice.
- The Barcelona citizen science office has received financial support from key funding programs at national level in Spain: the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) and “La Caixa Foundation”.
- Some research groups are already specialized in citizen science within the Catalan universities. At least 4 research groups has been working in this field since 2012 (e.g. the case of OpenSystems-Universitat de Barcelona)

WEAKNESSES

RRI

- Little knowledge / understanding of the RRI concept, its dimensions and practices by many of the agents in the R&I ecosystem
- High difficulty in “measuring” the RRI performance of the R+I ecosystem at regional level (MoRRI indicators are not applicable or difficult to measure)
- Lack of mainstreamed scientific literacy in society
- Science is not creatively addressed in early educational stages

Quadruple helix stakeholder engagement

- Lack of stable platforms or spaces for cooperative work between quadruple helix agents of the R&I ecosystem.
- Lack of participatory tradition of citizens, due to a historical-political heritage. Actions are commonly understood as complaining or opposition. There is still a pyramidal structure in society when it comes to raising and addressing territorial problems and challenges, which leads to the lack of stable structures that give citizens a voice.

Citizen Science

- Little knowledge about citizen science by most of the agents in the R&I ecosystem
- Citizen science initiatives are generally developed on an individual basis (at research group level), which limits their potential impact on a structural level.

- There are very few examples of public administrations embedding citizen science into their design and evaluation processes of public policies and services.
- Citizen science practices have not penetrated yet in the academia and research ecosystem. Citizen science and co-creation are scarcely introduced into the curricula of universities and research centers.
- Citizen science is being poorly supported financially by the public agencies: there are no specific funding programmes in Catalonia. Some funding is available in Spain through FECYT. The main source of funding comes from the H2020 Programme of the EC.
- The R&I private sector still has little role in the development of citizen science projects or those that include citizen participation.

OPPORTUNITIES

- RRI concept and dimension will be embedded in RIS3CAT 2021-2027 strategy as key elements, together with bottom-up approaches
- The Catalan ecosystem has a great diversity and is eager of increasing the interconnections to exchange experiences
- There is a large historical capacity of guild groupings that can be used as a lever point
- Growing interest on the part of public administration and academia to introduce co-creation and citizen participation within R&I processes, with a focus on improving public policies and services by bringing R&I closer to society
- The Catalan Think Tank on RRI & citizen science is gaining a lot of interest (approximately 60 major entities of the R&I ecosystem are participating)
- Important entities from different thematic areas of the R&I ecosystem (health, waste, water and environmental quality) are showing a high willingness to develop citizen science projects
- Recent creation of the “Commission for the promotion of citizen science & nature” (CICCNA) within the regional government's department of Territory and Sustainability

THREATS

- The current health crisis situation may cause political priorities to change and citizen participation to be discouraged: new and innovative methodologies are needed to enable participation
- Possible resistance or exhaustion on the part of citizens because they do not perceive that participatory processes have a real impact on public policies

- The priority of economic urgency constantly leads to no time to initiate transformative processes when making strategic decisions
- An excess of confidence in the results that 4H transformative processes can lead to an early abandonment of initiatives

How is the cluster using this analysis to define the action plan and the pilot strategy?

Think Tank activities and composition: the SWOT analysis shows that there is, on one hand, a strong willingness but, on the other hand, a lack of knowledge on how to increase citizens participation through innovative methodologies as citizen science. It is a need expressed by different agents of the 3H (different levels of public administrations, researchers and even companies). This need of deeper knowledge is the rationale behind the capacity building sessions that has already started to be implemented by the catalan cluster; it also explains why the Catalan Think Tank is composed by a variety of stakeholders, expecting to generate a collective reflection on how to embed RRI and citizen science in current projects and practices, from a perspective of quadruple helix stakeholder engagement. It is expected that this collective capacity building will generate specific ideas and proposals for the organizations to be implemented.

The SWOT analysis also shows the difficulty of measuring the RRI performance of the region or even the positive impact of projects developed with this perspective. Regarding this need, the Think Tank (mainly the core group, composed of key policy makers) will also contribute to the co-creation of a framework for evaluating RRI performance and impact.

Pilot projects: the SWOT analysis shows that there are existing public fundings and local strategies that are trying to integrate deep citizen participation as part of the procedures. This interest is shown at different levels and applied to different thematic areas: waste management is one of those. This constitutes an opportunity for TRANSFORM to link pilot projects to existing policies and initiatives, with the aim of increasing and spreading the impact of TRANSFORM activities.

4.5 Brussels-Capital cluster

4.5.1 Experts involved in the SWOT analysis

The experts involved in the SWOT analysis of the Brussels-Capital region were BE participation, Innoviris, UCLouvain and MAD Brussels.

4.5.2 Results of the SWOT analysis

STRENGTHS

Cluster composition:

- Cluster with diversified expertise, multidisciplinary team & diversity of methodological approaches
- Motivation of the group to achieve substantial results over a long period (3 years) which will make it possible to have a real impact

TRANSFORM/EU project framework:

- TRANSFORM allows to focus on both theory and practice
- TRANSFORM is an international project with different cultures of practice (horizontal) which can be inspiring for the Brussels cluster.

Theme:

- High potential of the theme 'circular economy & innovation'

Methodology:

- Set up a reproducible methodology
- Create a model of citizen participation, exemplary and competitive
- Develop an efficient and innovative methodology
- Give a good example illustrating our co-creation method
- Recognition of the importance of citizen engagement in decision-making processes.

Citizen in the centre:

- Opportunity to tackle concrete citizen (community) needs with concrete solutions
- Potential for citizen ownership of the project
- Align the collective interest and sustainability

Decision-making and policy formulation:

- Long-term impact on Research & Innovation policies
- TRANSFORM has the potential of a collective project to mobilize responsible policies
- Federate regional dynamics and actors of the transition
- Contribute to a sustainable society in economic transition
- Have an impact on regional RRI policies
- Align the field with (inter) national (vertical) policy.
- Objectives in line with the political intentions of the region and presence of the Innovation Agency in the cluster (Innoviris)

WEAKNESSES

- Scale of action: limited understanding of large-scale dynamics that could impact the pilot that the cluster will co-develop.
- No private sector representative in the consortium
- Choice of approach, make sure that the bottom-up approach is really used because community needs have not yet been identified
- Work on the field still in experimentation
- Different ambitions and visions among cluster members
- First experience in this type of project / with this consortium

OPPORTUNITIES

- The regional context: intensity of the Brussels social network, and multitude of actions, programs and existing projects.
- Hope that after the Covid-19 crisis society will be more open to a change in the way it operates in the way of organizing research with more participatory approaches, to the desire to "relocate" the economy
- Number of existing potential regional partners

RISKS

Political and economic crisis (COVID-19):

- The economic crisis can impact the participating audiences.
- The different orientations of a potential future regional government in Brussels.
- A civil society less motivated to engage

Project sustainability:

- Difficulties in making the project autonomous and sustainable.
- Disappearance of the project and difficulty in finding carriers after the end of the funding
- Co-creation process: less empirical data available on this type of process

Ambition vs. Reality:

- Risk that the objectives of TRANSFORM are not in line with the expectations of the public in the region, that they are disconnected from the realities of the field.
- Development of a project that is unrealistic or impossible to anchor in the field

Other:

- Impossibility of measuring and showing the positive impact / added value of the pilot and the experiments that will be developed in the cluster.
- Risk that the TRANSFORM approach is not widely used.

4.6 Presentation of common critical elements to the three SWOT analysis

Common strengths

- **The three regional administrations are committed to the objectives of the project - All** cluster members believe TRANSFORM has a strong innovative potential
- Lombardy: Open Innovation Platform and willingness of Lombardy Region to listen to stakeholders and willingness to listen from Lombardy Region around science and society issues (reflexivity)
- Catalonia: Public administration leadership & experience in RRI and stakeholder engagement
- Brussels-Capital: Objectives in line with the political intentions of the region and presence of the Innovation Agency in the cluster (Innoviris)

2. Strong methodological frameworks are in place in the three regions:

- Lombardy: Experience in participative methodology for agenda settings
- Catalonia: Academia leadership in citizen science
- Brussels-Capital: Cluster with diversified expertise, multidisciplinary team & diversity of methodological approaches

3. All of the three regional administrations have elements of RRI in place:

- Lombardy: Institutionalisation of RRI with the law “Lombardy is Research and Innovation”. RRI language and terminology already adopted (i.e. in the PST)
- Catalonia: The regional administration has already participated in other European projects devoted to embedding RRI in RIS3 (SeeRRI) – also funded by SwafS-14 + RRI concept and dimension will be embedded in RIS3CAT 2021-2027 strategy as key elements, together with bottom-up approaches.
- Brussels-Capital: Cocreate programme of Innoviris.

Common weaknesses

1. RRI understanding and measurement

- Catalonia: High difficulty in “measuring” the RRI performance of the R+I ecosystem at regional level (MoRRI indicators are not applicable or difficult to measure)
- Brussels-Capital: Impossibility of measuring and showing the added value of the pilot and the experiments that will be developed in the cluster.

2. Ambition vs. Reality:

- Catalonia: An excess of confidence in the results that 4H transformative processes can lead to an early abandonment of initiatives
- Brussels-Capital: Risk that the objectives of TRANSFORM are not in line with the expectations of the public in the region, that they are disconnected from the realities of the field.

3. Meaningful citizens engagement?

- Lombardy: Risk to exploit the contribution from citizens without involving them in the following steps of the innovation process
- Brussels-Capital: Make sure that the bottom-up approach is really used. The community needs have not yet been identified

4. Few RRI elements are included in regional calls

- Lombardy: Need to include RRI terminology (and criteria) in the regional calls
- Catalonia: Little knowledge / understanding of the RRI concept, its dimensions and practices by many of the agents in the R&I ecosystem

Common opportunities

1. Interest of the R&I ecosystems to participate

- Lombardy: RRI as a tool for research and innovation advancement/ survival
- Catalonia: Growing interest on the part of public administration and academia to introduce co-creation and citizen participation within R&I processes, with a focus on improving public policies and services by bringing R&I closer to society

2. Great diversity of regional R&I ecosystems

- Lombardy: Lombardia Innovativa: mapping organisations that conduct co-creation activities with final users

- Catalonia: The Catalan ecosystem has a great diversity and is eager of increasing the interconnections to exchange experiences
- Brussels-Capital: The regional context: intensity of the Brussels social network, and multitude of actions, programs and existing projects.

Common risks

1. Current COVID-19 crisis

- Catalonia: The current health crisis situation may cause political priorities to change and citizen participation to be discouraged: new and innovative methodologies are needed to enable participation
- Brussels-Capital: The economic crisis can impact the target audiences. The different orientations of a potential future regional government in Brussels.

2. Lack of trust from citizen that their contribution will have an impact

- Catalonia: Possible resistance or exhaustion on the part of citizens because they do not perceive that participatory processes have a real impact on public policies

4.7 Result of the collaborative exercise to complement the SWOT analysis

In this part of the workshop, the participants worked in two groups to draw some conclusions from the identified common critical elements from the SWOT analysis. Discussions took place about the common strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and risks that the three clusters encounter.

The participative session was based on a tool that enables to combine the SWOT components, to develop a synthesis to take the most out of the analysis.

In that context the groups were asked to answer the question presented in the table below:

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can strengths be maximized? • How can strengths be used to take advantage of opportunities? • How can strengths be used to reduce threats? 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How can weaknesses be minimised? • How can weaknesses be corrected to take advantage of opportunities? • How strengths can overcome weaknesses
<p>Opportunities How can opportunities be maximised?</p>	<p>Threats How can threats be minimised?</p>

Table3. Questions discussed during the collaborative exercise to complement this map of common critical elements

4.7.1 Strengths

- Common strengths identified can be maximised by:

a. Taking action:

- turning commitment of the three regional administrations to the objectives of the project into actions.
- translating the political commitment in concrete actions, first starting with sharing and building up internal knowledge on RRI, to be sure that there is a common language and a common understanding on what clusters think and consider important in RRI.
- putting more concrete RRI actions in place with exchange of experiences among the three TRANSFORM clusters.
- planning a sustainable path for RRI implementation (beyond TRANSFORM)
- producing strong pilots/participative actions with the idea that ‘less is more’. They should be able to show the path and also carefully cocreate/codesign/plan them.
- organising RRI capacity building

b. Multistakeholder engagement:

- involving clusters and the broader active RRI communities in the three territories.
- finding ways to involve many and diverse actors from the ecosystem

c. Influence policies and actions of public regional authorities:

- showing usefulness and reassuring regional governments that TRANSFORM clusters can deliver activities, processes and actions they need/would like to have.
- following the current process implemented by public administrations embedding RRI principles in most RIS3.
- converting commitment into methodologies to deliver policies. There should not only be principles formulated but formal processes implemented. RRI is a costly exercise: unless it becomes a necessary link in the chain, it will be felt as an additional cost not a necessary, structural one. Processes should have measures for performance and outcomes.
- The development of stable platforms, communities of practices, commissions, funding programmes by regional governments to foster RRI & stakeholder engagement. Regional government should act as promoters and facilitators.

- detecting what specific positive impact relies on TRANSFORM methodologies used in the three clusters that can be useful for policy makers.
- introducing RRI elements in public calls for proposals as requirements.

Common strengths identified that can be used to reduce threats:

a. COVID-19 crisis:

- finding actions that can be undertaken even if the lockdown remains for a certain period of time.

b. Citizen distrust/fatigue of citizens:

- showing concretely what the clusters deliver with their pilot activities.
- using participatory approaches to involve citizens for recovery plan and actions

c. Lack of RRI understanding and measurement:

- supporting the emergence of new KPIs to support administrations focussing more and more their RDI policy on RRI principles with a need for impact evaluation.

4.7.2 Weaknesses

The common weaknesses that can be addressed and minimised:

a. The lack of understanding and measurement of RRI:

- improving the collaboration between the WP2 and WP7. The COVID-19 crisis does not help with the collaboration but it can be mitigated. Deeper interaction intra-consortium on this line of work is needed.
- connecting closely with the clusters and their pilot to develop meaningful KPIs for the process, and the outcomes helping to assess what the added value is for each step.

b. The lack of trust of citizens towards participative processes:

- not generating false expectations: transformative processes are slow.
- reconsidering how to work with very different stakeholders to make their needs appear when confronted to a pilot.
- making sure stakeholders know what the R&I ecosystem in each region is: WHO, HOW MANY, WHERE
- supporting capacity building and awareness raising activities in place at cluster individual level and among the three clusters to focus on understanding and not just information.
- anticipating a plan for sustainability in capacity building and awareness raising activities.

- increasing cooperation with diverse stakeholders (4Helix) while participative actions of each pilot are implemented and progress.

c. The discrepancy between ambition and reality:

- implementing concrete actions and not only spending time in discussions. Less is more, but the less has to be real, “walking the walk” and not just “talking the talk”.

The common weaknesses identified can be corrected, taking advantage of opportunities by:

- using the richness of the think tank/RRI communities in each cluster to plan a capacity building process with concrete and local examples of RRI actions
- testing and developing relevant KPIs to measure impact of RRI in regional policies.

4.7.3 Opportunities

The common identified opportunities can be maximised by:

- using the platforms related to R&I and stakeholders dialogue in place in the three regions, with the help of the regional administration, to share surveys on S3, to involve citizens in participative processes, etc.
- reflecting about the way institutions are trying to find values in the current context of COVID-19 and all citizen activities being done online. In this context, there is an opportunity to be valuable to the community partners and think of equity. The fact that a real time record of what is happening online is available is an opportunity, as the resource does not only belong to the organising institutions, it provides more ownership to other actors.
- involving the private sector as adopting RRI for enterprises make it more align to the market

4.7.4 Threats

Common threats identified in the three clusters and strategies to minimise them:

a. The challenge to have sufficient citizen participation:

- Repeating activities several times, having a shorter timeline and being flexible with the content of the participative sessions. The typical development timeline of 6 months minimum in participative processes is proving to be too slow because the employees/civil servants in the institutions are fast changing, especially in these circumstances.
- giving feedback to citizens all along the process, not only in the creation process but also during the implementation.

- being clear about the impact expected, how the results are presented and shared and to clarify the expectations to the citizens.
- coaching participants especially for the policy step of the participative process, defining a shared vocabulary and making sure the terminology is changed according to the actors targeted.
- creating a common space for citizens, public administration actors, and other key actors to meet.

b. The challenge of regular change of priorities at institutional level:

- by focussing on a selling point to achieve this participation and adapt to the change of perspective.

5. Societal, economic, geographical and environmental frameworks in which the participatory actions will be developed

As specified earlier, the aim of T2.3 was to help regional clusters to reflect on their place within the larger societal, geographical, economic and environmental framework while planning cluster activities. To understand the rationale behind this task it is important to come back to the central aim of the TRANSFORM project, which is to open up regional R&I activities to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation. Partners of the project will set-up activities to open-up R&I actions by testing and disseminating co-creation methodological frameworks for the implementation of Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3). These co-creation methodologies are specific in each region but all rely on quadruple helix engagement with a particular focus on citizen engagement. To be able to implement these methodologies a key step is to understand the societal needs of the citizens that will be involved in co-creation processes as well as the economic, geographical and environmental frameworks of the R&I ecosystems.

The three societal, economic, geographical and environmental frameworks in which participatory activities will be developed, described in this chapter, encompass the elements that are particular to each region and the local areas concerned. There are the elements of the frameworks that have an influence or need to be taken into account in the choice of cluster activities and process they will put in place.

5.1 Lombardy Cluster frameworks

5.1.1 Societal and economic frameworks

Lombardy has 10 million people (approximately 1/6 of the Italian population) and produces about 22% of the national GDP (2019). Its employment rate is constantly higher than the national average. Compared to the other Italian regions, Lombardy has historically been characterized by a high propensity for innovation, favored by the simultaneous presence of public and private actors, whose interaction has often led to the emergence of new ideas, solutions, and applications.

Compared to the rest of the country, Lombardy provides:

- 21% of the national R&D spending

- 27% of the most cited scientific research
- 32% of patents in Italy

According to the [Regional Innovation Scoreboard](#) Index 2019, Lombardy is very strong compared to some indicators such as employment medium and high tech manufacturing and knowledge-intensive services, trademark applications, SMEs Innovating in-house, product or process innovators. However, it has a below-average performance in R&D expenditure public sector, innovative SMEs collaborating with others, EPO patent application, lifelong learning. Its economic system is mainly focused on small- and medium-sized enterprises (approx. 800,000), but it is reinforced by the presence of large industrial groups.

Figure 7 - Lombardy Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2019

Lombardy economy is specialized in all the traditional Made in Italy domains such as fashion and furniture-decoration, but also in all the new technology-dominated ones, such as electronics, industrial automation, and robotics. Lately, Lombardy Regional government created 9 [Regional Technology Clusters](#), which are development poles with high technology potential linked to the knowledge and industrial assets of the region:

- Agri-food;
- Aerospace;
- Green Chemistry;
- Energy, Construction and Environment;

- Smart Factory;
- Land and Sea Mobility;
- Life Sciences;
- Smart Communities Technology;
- Living Environment Technology.

Regarding research in companies, recent studies indicate an increasingly widespread propensity in the Lombardy manufacturing sector: almost 60% of companies declare that they have carried out R&D research in the three-year period 2015-2017. 28% of employees work in the most advanced manufacturing sectors. 22% of knowledge-intensive startups in Italy are based in Lombardy.

Human capital represents a priority to be strengthened as it constitutes a fundamental enabling factor for the attractiveness and competitiveness and the ground for the quality of the entire innovation process. The propensity for innovative collaboration in micro-enterprise networks and redirection towards new technologies, with the involvement of a large number of Lombardy universities, must be improved.

With 50,000 agricultural enterprises, 37% of the national milk production, 42% of the national rise production and 7.69 billion euros, Lombardy is also the first agricultural Italian Region⁷.

The lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the modest level of skills and digital infrastructures, which resulted in 49% of smart work in Milan, Lodi, and Monza and Brianza areas (compared to the 35% at the national level)⁸.

Taking into consideration the digitization of the Public Administration, Lombardy, although below the European average, is the most digitized Italian region. The performance of municipalities is good in terms of access to digital services and the provision of wireless local networks, while the use of videoconferencing tools by municipal administrations and ICT training for staff are still poor.

Available data do not officially describe yet the variation of poverty rate in Lombardy caused by COVID-19 pandemic which, unfortunately, is likely to increase. In 2018 the rate of absolute poverty in families was 5.9% (compared to 7% at the national level) and 15.7% of people were at risk of poverty and social exclusion (compared to 27.3% at the national level). Addressing inequalities and economic recovery has been identified as priorities of LR and are informing its planning activity for the next years.

Lombardy Region performs the measurement of the 16 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by comparing Lombardy with the 21 European countries belonging to the OECD (using historical series analysis and composite indices). The composite indices, calculated for each of the SDGs, allowed the

⁷ www.regione.lombardia.it/wps/portal/istituzionale/HP/DettaglioRedazionale/scopri-la-lombardia/economia/lombardia-prima-regione-agricola

⁸ Assolombarda (2020), [Booklet Economia. La Lombardia nel confronto nazionale ed europeo](#), Centro Studi n. 44/2020

construction of rankings between territories and positioning Lombardy in each of the objectives so as to provide a concise reading of the trends.

In the last performance of Lombardy Region (2020):

- for most of the objectives (9) there are signs of improvement (value above 100 in green): Goal 3 Health and wellbeing; Goal 4 Education quality; Goal 5 Gender Equality; Goal 7 Clean and accessible energy; Goal 8 Decent work and economic growth; Goal 9 Innovation and infrastructure; Goal 12 Consumption e responsible production; Goal 16 Peace, justice and strong institutions; Goal 17 Partnership for the goals;
- for 3 objectives, a worsening of performance is observed (lower value at 100 in red): Goal 1 Defeat poverty; Goal 2 Defeat hunger; Goal 10 Reduce inequalities;
- stability emerges for 3 objectives (value close to 100 in orange): Goal 6 Clean water and sanitation; Goal 11 Sustainable cities and communities; Goal 13 Fight against climate change.

5.1.2 Geographical and Environmental frameworks

Lombardy is one of the Italian Regions with the highest soil consumption, 290.000 ha, which is 12% of the entire regional surface (compared to the 7.1% registered at the national level). Forests cover 26% of the Lombardy territory, corresponding to 616 m² for inhabitants, but this rate is unequally distributed among the different regional Provinces, with the highest being 6,908 m² per capita (Sondrio Province) and the lower being 27 m² (Milan Province). Also, for this reason, a high percentage of Lombardy forests are under some forms of protection (i.e. Regional or National parks, hydro-geological obligations, etc.) and urban green areas are being introduced for compensation (also to mitigate urban heat islands). Overall, the Lombardy forestry embraces 77,000 ha, absorbing 4,9 Mt

carbon tons. Furthermore, 69% of the Lombardy territory is dedicated to agricultural cultivations, with only 2.8% of them being organic.

Lombardy glaciers cover 87.67 km², representing 23.95% of the Italian glaciers. In the '50s their extension was 115 km², but since then it has reduced by 24% and their melting rate has increased in the last decades.

Furthermore, in Lombardy the state of conservation of most habitats cannot be considered positively: in 74% of cases, it is described as bad or inadequate. With regards to soil contamination, there is an increase in the number of remediated sites (+87% since 2012), but also an increase in the contamination of new sites (+16% since 2018).

Air quality is one of the most urgent environmental challenges for Lombardy: according to the UE parameters, the thresholds for PM₁₀, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), as well as for PM_{2.5}, and tropospheric ozone have been exceeded by Lombardy in the last years and for this reason, the Region has to answer to a series of infringements procedures from the European Commission. More in details, the daily limit of PM₁₀ (50 µg/ m³), which should not be exceeded for more than 35 days in a year, has not been respected in almost all the districts capitals: Brescia, Cremona, Lodi, Mantova, Milan, Monza e Pavia. CO₂ emissions in Lombardy are mainly due to natural gas plants (20%), residential buildings (19%), diesel vehicles (15%), gasoline vehicles (6%), bio-refinery (5%), and cattle farming (4%).

The residential sector in Lombardy scores first in terms of energy consumption (representing 29.2% of the total energy consumption of the region, corresponding to 7.3 million tons) and a series of energy efficiency policies are being put in place. The rate of energy production from renewable energy sources (RES) in Lombardy is constantly increasing, reaching 14.9% of the entire RES national production.

Waste production is also a key element for the environmental sustainability of the Lombardy Region. Recycling has reached 71% in 2019, but recycled waste production per capita in 2019 (6.43 Kg) has increased by 8.28% compared to 2018 and special waste production in Lombardy has also increased in the last years (+4.6% from 2017 to 2018). Considering regional, inter-regional and imported products, the whole waste released in the Italian plants has increased from 10,348,668 tons (2014) to 12,614,040 tons (2018). Also, outgoing waste has increased from 8.954.409 to 10.077.207 tons.

Waste food production is also quite important in Lombardy, as at the whole national level, counting 0.88% of Italian GDP and it has increased due to the pandemics. In Lombardy, on September the 23rd 2020, the sales within the mass distribution networks have increased by 89% compared to 2019.

Statistics do not show yet how the economic crisis is impacting on indicators described above. Addressing climate change and promoting the transition to the green economy have been identified as priorities of LR and are informing its planning activity for the next years.

5.2 Catalan cluster frameworks

5.2.1 Geographical and societal framework

Catalonia consists of four provinces: Barcelona, Girona, Lleida, and Tarragona. The capital and largest city, Barcelona is the second-most populated municipality in Spain and the fifth-most populous urban area in the European Union. It is bordered by France, Andorra, the Mediterranean, and the Spanish autonomous communities of Aragon and Valencia. The official languages are Catalan, Spanish, and the Aranese dialect of Occitan.

Barcelona is among the most visited cities in Europe. Catalan culture, architecture and history have developed its own unique and universal identity over the centuries.

With 7.5 million inhabitants and a surface area of 32,108 square kilometres, Catalonia is a diverse territory, with extensive mountains, inland depressions, and a coastline that stretches for 214 km. Catalonia has a marked geographical diversity, considering the small size of its territory. The geography is defined by the Mediterranean coast (580 km of coastline), and large relief units of the Pyrenees to the north and the Catalan center depression.

The hydrographic network can be divided in two sectors, the Ebro river slope (occidental) and the oriental slope constituted by minor rivers that flow to the Mediterranean along the Catalan coast. The first one channels approximately 10 times more water than the second one.

A highly industrialized land, the nominal GDP of Catalonia in 2018 was €228 billion (second after the community of Madrid, €230 billion) and the per capita GDP was €30,426 (\$32,888).

The unemployment rate stood at 11.5% in 2018 and was lower than the national average. The at-risk-of-poverty rate was 31% in 2019.

5.2.2 Economic framework

Historically a trading nation, Catalonia's economic activity has always depended on its ability to connect to the rest of the world. Its location in the Mediterranean and its transport infrastructures, as

well as its trading, entrepreneurial and open economy have made it a top rank strategic position in the south of Europe with Barcelona as an unbeatable meeting point for international business.

The distribution of economic sectors is the following:

- Agriculture: 1,3%.
- Industry and Energy: 18,3%
- Construction: 6,4%
- Services: 73,7%

In the context of the financial crisis of 2007–2008, Catalonia was expected to suffer a recession amounting to almost a 2% contraction of its regional GDP in 2009 but in recent years its economy recovered a positive evolution and the GDP grew 3.3% in 2015.

Nevertheless, the COVID crisis is producing a new contraction effect on the economy, which consequences and length are difficult to foresee at the moment. For example, industrial sector has decreased over a 30%, while hotel and catering industry has decrease over a 80%.

Since 2009, the export capacity of the economy has increased significantly. The trade surplus with Spain is maintained in parallel with an increasing orientation of Catalan exports to international markets since 2009.

The EU concentrates 64.3 % of Catalan exports. The main markets are France (16.2 %), Germany (10.4 % and Italy (8.6 %). During the period 2012-2018, the number of companies that export regularly increased strongly (24.9%). In 2018, out of 47,918 exporting firms (with exports over 50,000 euros), 7,624 exported regularly.

The industrial activity, which represents nearly 21% of the Catalan GDP, has grown particularly in the Barcelona area, and it has also developed in many industrial cities all over the country. Half of the Catalan economy has either a direct or indirect relationship with the industrial sector, innovative, dynamic and diversified.

Food, chemicals, motor vehicles, energy and pharma are the main industrial sectors. And today, this strong industrial base and a powerful ICT sector are key elements making Catalonia a driving force in industry 4.0. Catalonia has shown its commitment to 3D printing, it is leading the field in connected vehicle testing, in robotics applied to intelligent logistics management systems or in excellence in big data. And many companies are firmly committed to Barcelona, the Mobile World Capital to do business and develop technology here.

Together with industry, trade and tourism are important activities. Tourism accounts for 12% of Catalan GDP and has become one of the most notable economic activities. With more than 19 million foreign tourists (2018), Catalonia is one of the top European destinations showing 22.2% of the Spanish total tourist accommodation places and 2.5% of the EU.

Catalonia and Barcelona are very well positioned in international rankings:

<p>European cities and regions of the future 2018/2019 FDI Magazine</p> <p>Cities of the world with the best reputation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Tokyo 2 Sydney 3 Copenhagen 4 Vienna 5 Stockholm 6 Venice 7 Rome 8 Zurich 9 Munich 10 Montreal (...) 15 Barcelona 					
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According to the EC regional competitiveness and innovation indexes, Catalonia is classified in the group of the moderate regions.

Regional Competitiveness Index, 2019

Regional Innovation Index, 2019

Catalonia's indicators of the Regional Innovation Index, 2019

Source: European Commission

Total R&D expenditure amounts 1.52 % of GDP. 61.1 % of this expenditure is private (data for 2018).

- **Environmental framework**

Catalonia is very rich in natural scenery, with 18 sites declared to be natural parks and protected areas.

Air quality

In 2015, the general situation in Catalonia will be complementing the majority of air quality objectives according to current regulations. From 15 pollutants, 10 complete all air quality objectives in all areas, and most of them register a lower level than the maximum permeability. In addition, there are 5 pollutants that have not met the quality objectives of air: nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), tropospheric oxide (O₃) sulphur d'hydrogen (H₂S), suspended particles PM₁₀ i el benzo(a)pirè (BaP).

Water quality

In 2007, the water quality assessment was initiated according to the requirements of the Water Framework Directive. Three types of indicators are measured: biological, hydromorphological and physical-chemical, in types of surface and underground water masses.

In 2015, from 50% of water masses evaluated, the 23% of the water masses had obvious signs of alteration that make their status still inferior to good (16%) or near to good (15%). Just a 19% had the status of good quality.

Biodiversity

There are more than 600 different types of habitats in Catalonia, 94 of which belong to the category of habitats of community interest (HIC). In all Europe there are 198 HICs (figure 5.1). These habitats occupy just over 33% of the surface area of Catalonia (1,059,139.6 hectares), and are equivalent to 46% of the Natura 2000 network. Of these 94 HIC, 22 are of priority interest (Europe has no 61).

It is calculated that there are more than 30,000 species in Catalonia, so there are large groups of which many species remain to be identified, such as fongs or non-arthropod invertebrates.

The number of protected natural areas in Catalonia in 2015 is 184, and they occupy 31.77% of the territory. In 2006 the name and area of protected natural areas in Catalonia will increase with the approval of the Catalan proposal for the Natura 2000 network, made up of special conservation areas and areas of special protection for those who are not. The areas included in this network will automatically become part of the PEIN.

There are more than 900 public forests in Catalonia, occupying an area of 490,000 hectares approximately (23% of the forest area of the country). By 2015, of the total number of public forests, 460 were managed with an instrument of forest management (IOF). The surface area of these forests is 255,960.99 hectares (Table 5.7).

In Catalonia, the majority of the forest area and number of forests are privately owned. These estates, in the same way as public estates, are managed with forest management instruments (IOF). In 2015, there were 3473 hectares in force with 452279 hectares under management.

5.3 Brussels-Capital cluster frameworks

5.3.1 General considerations

The Brussels-Capital region cluster will facilitate the co-creation of social innovation solutions based on an original vision of the circular economy, inscribed in the urban ecosystem, linked to the territories. The work on the selected innovations will be carried out through a process based on design thinking developed by ELI-UCLouvain: an iterative process where the initial design and impact evaluation of an

innovation is deconstructed and reconstructed participatively enabling a multidimensional (economic, social, environmental and on the public health) assessment of the potential impacts of the innovation. This process will rely on quadruple helix engagement with a particular focus on citizen engagement through civil society associations. To be able to implement these participative activities, the Brussels-Capital cluster performed an intensive reflection work to understand the societal needs and the economic, geographical and environmental frameworks particular to the Brussels-Capital region and its R&I ecosystem. These elements that have an influence or need to be taken into account in the choice of cluster activities are presented below.

5.3.2 Societal, Economic, Geographical and Environmental framework

To introduce this framework analysis and understand the explanations provided below, it is important to provide **some general indicators** regarding the population of the Brussels-Capital region. The number of inhabitants (1st January 2019) in Belgium is 11,431,406 and in Brussels-Capital region, 1,208,542 (10,6% of national population).⁹

Key aspects related to society or social relations in Brussels-Capital region are summarized below:¹⁰

- 7,441 inhabitants/km² (2019).
- 33,356 euros/year of expenses / household (34% housing and 17% food)
- Qualification of the people of 25 years+: 4/10 has a higher education diploma and 3/10 secondary school diploma
- 422,097 inhabitants of non-belgian nationality (7/10 from EU 28; 180 nationalities).
- 110,825 entreprises (96% with less than 10 workers; 12,241 created in 2019).
- Employment market in Belgium: 706,250 employments (½ occupied by commuting workers).
- Average age: 36,2 for man and 38,4 for women - Life expectancy: 79 for man and 83,4 for women
- 1.2 millions inhabitants (23% under 18 years; 35% non-Belgian nationality, 21% isolated)
- 162 km² of superficy with 25% of green spaces
- 6.6 millions nights in hotels
- 84 billions euros of PIB (92% services; 5% others; 3% industry)

These first general figures related to the Brussels-Capital region enable us to form a first picture of the context in which the Brussels pilot will be developed. In terms of **demography**, the region has a very high density, the 15th most densely populated region of EU¹¹, which has an impact on the urban

⁹ IBSA perspective Bruxelles, chiffres clés de la région de Bruxelles-Capitale, retrieved on Internet on 26 November 2020:

<https://ibsa.brussels/chiffres/chiffres-cles-de-la-region>

¹⁰ IBSA, Idem

¹¹ EUROSTAT, Your key to European statistics - 06/04/2017. retrieved from Internet on 15 November 2020

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20170406->

ecosystem, housing, pollution and quality of life has elaborated later in the section. The region is the capital of Europe, Brussels is the second most cosmopolitan city in the world. The **multicultural and multi-nationalities aspects of the population** is a key element to take into account for a citizen engagement process on the territory. The **economic context** of the region is characterized by an overwhelming majority of small enterprises which defines the nature of the private sector on the territory and should be taken into account for the quadruple helix engagement. Finally, the region is a central hub for workers in the country, with a significant number of commuters, this situation has an important impact from a **social point of view** and on **environmental aspects**, another key point defining the regional context.

In the next parts of the section, the most important elements to take into account for the Brussels-Capital cluster of TRANSFORM are elaborated.

- **Societal aspects**

The understanding of 'societal' in this section are the elements that relate to the various aspects of the social life of individuals, in the sense that they constitute an organised society. The two major domains of societal aspects developed here are the socio-economic, demographic and socio-cultural aspects (density of population, access to housing, quality of life, employment rates, etc..) and the research and innovation aspects.

Social aspects

The density of population is 374 per m² in Belgium and 7,501 in Brussels-Capital Region, a very high density of population compared to the average situation at national level.¹²

The 20 most densely populated districts of Belgium are all located in Brussels-Capital region (BCR). Brussels with its agglomeration (19 districts) has more than 1.2 million inhabitants making it the most populated metropolis in the country with the highest density.

The challenges faced by the public authorities to guarantee an optimal **quality of life** for the entire population are numerous, particularly in terms of infrastructure, public facilities and services to the population. A **number of key challenges** appear in this region including the reduction of the **precariousness** which remains a reality for a large number of inhabitants of Brussels, the reduction of the growing **pressure on the environment**, and the coordination of various functions of the city. These

[1?inheritRedirect=true#:~:text=Paris%20%2D%20the%20most%20densely%20populated,are%20in%20the%20United%20Kingdom](#)

¹² Statbel, la Belgique en chiffres, retrieved from internet on 15 November 2020: <https://statbel.fgov.be/fr/themes/population/densite-de-la-population#figures>

questions shed light on the issues surrounding the announced densification of the Brussels Region.¹³ The TRANSFORM cluster in the region is willing to take this situation into account, to make sure this social reality is represented in the participative process and be as much as possible, inclusive in the approach of the pilot.

Looking at the sub-regional dynamics of the **population growth**, notable differences emerge on the territory. Between 2008 and 2018, the population increased by 14% in the region. But this growth rate varies from 4% to Watermael-Boitsfort, 20% to the City of Brussels. In general, the central districts (pentagon and first ring) of the Region often know a more marked migratory intensity, in particular neighborhoods of the “poor crescent”. So it is in this area, where rents are relatively lower and housing less sanitary, where the population density is the highest within the Region, that the **tensions in terms of access to quality housing** are the highest.

Migration dynamics also influence the composition of the population, the most disadvantaged districts of the Region are characterized among other things by the arrival of a large number of people with an poor or intermediary immigrant background and the departure of populations residents to other municipalities. A significant part of the population living in poverty is enabled to change accommodation (despite sometimes insalubrity problems) and therefore is characterized by residential stability, and another part leaves the Brussels Region in the face of social pressures, financial and urban¹⁴.

This key challenge of **access to housing** is one of the important elements the cluster will take into account as a theme for its participatory activities related to social R&I for the region. In recent decades, the number of households has grown faster than the number of housing in the Brussels Region. Indeed, between 2001 and 2017, the number of private households increased by 70,523 units while the number of housing has increased only by 61,751 units. In addition, the particularly high rents and selling prices, the dilapidated state of buildings and the high poverty of the inhabitants of Brussels mean that a significant part of the population lives in overcrowded, poor quality housing, or even finds itself in some cases without their own housing¹⁵.

Income inequalities are more marked in the Brussels Region than across the country and in other cities. In addition to the pressure on the demand for housing at the quantitative level, the presence of

¹³ IBSA, Idem

¹⁴ Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale (2019), Précarités, mal-logement et expulsions domiciliaires en Région bruxelloise, Cahier thématique du Rapport bruxellois sur l'état de la pauvreté 2018, Commission communautaire commune : Bruxelles., p14. Retrieved from internet on 24 November: https://www.ccc-ggc.brussels/sites/default/files/documents/graphics/rapport-pauvrete/pauvrete_expulsion_fr_0.pdf

¹⁵ Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale (2019), idem p.16

people with high incomes in the territory also contributes to the general increase in real estate prices and rents.¹⁶

This **social polarization in Brussels** is confirmed by the indicator related to the median tax income of declarations by district. In the figure below, it is possible to see the disparity of revenues according to districts ranging from less than 17,00 euros per year in city centre districts to more than 23,000 euros per year in more peripheral districts of the region.

REVENUS ET DÉPENSES DES MÉNAGES

REVENU IMPOSABLE MÉDIAN DES DÉCLARATIONS
PAR QUARTIER EN 2016¹
Euros par déclaration

Sources : IBSA, Statbel (Statistique fiscale des revenus)
Monitoring des Quartiers - IBSA © Brussels UrbIS ©
¹ Exercice 2017, revenus 2016

Figure 8 - MEDIAN TAX INCOME OF DECLARATIONS BY DISTRICT IN 2016

In relation to the socio-economic characteristics of the population in Brussels, an indicator interesting to look at is the **repartition of the population in age of working**. 803,800 people are in age of working and among this population, 526,800 are active while 276,900 are inactive (34,5% of total population in age of working) among which **70,300 are benefiting from unemployment benefits (13,4% of total population in age of working)**, as presented in the report from IBSA (Brussels institute for statistics and analysis)¹⁷. This unemployment rate of 13,4% provides a valuable measure of the mismatches between the labour supply and demand, highlighting the part of the working class unutilized labour supply. Of course this indicator cannot be taken alone, as it focuses on the share of persons in the labour force who are unemployed.

Another important element of the socio-economic framework of Brussels-Capital Region for the participative activities the cluster will implement in year 2 and 3 of the project is the fact that residents

¹⁶ Observatoire de la Santé et du Social de Bruxelles-Capitale (2019), idem p.18

¹⁷ IBSA - perspectives Bruxelles, Mini-Bru La Région de Bruxelles-Capitale en chiffres 2020, Éditions IRIS – D/2020/6374/288 © 2020 Région de Bruxelles-Capitale, retrieved from Internet on 23 November 2020 from: https://ibsa.brussels/sites/default/files/publication/documents/Mini-Bru_2020-FR-WEB.pdf

are the citizens that can afford the rent, and workers sometimes live far away and bear the greatest transportation costs. **Access to work is problematic and it implies a reduction in the quality of life.** A significant movement of population commuting to work in other regions than their place of residence exists. A large majority of Brussels population in employment is working in the Brussels-Capital region (82,5%). In addition to these residents working in their region, 226,400 people are commuting from Flanders and 129,600 from Wallonia to work in the Brussels-Capital region. Of the total number of people working in the Brussels-Capital region (732,600), 48,6% so, almost half of this population (356,000) is residing in one of the two other regions, commuting to access the working place.

Research and Development / Research and Innovation

Key aspects interesting in the context of the core objective of TRANSFORM related to research and innovation and to R&D have been presented in section 3.3 Research and Innovation ecosystems in Brussels-Capital. To complement the information provided about the programme of R&I and the S3 of the region, some general indicators characterizing the regional context are presented in this section and the relation between R&D and economy are presented in the next subsection.

The figure below shows the evolution of public budget funding for R&D in the region. A an increase can be observed from 2010 to 2018 (almost 35 millions euros to more than 45millions in 2018) with a slight diminution in 2011 and 2013 and a stagnation from 2014 to 2015.

Source : Belspo
¹ Sur base des données budgétaires initiales

Figure 9 - evolution of public budget funding for R&D in the region in millions of euros

Concerning the repartition of people, staff working in R&D (ETP) by sector of execution in 2017 in Brussels-Capital region, the private sector is the most important employers with 46,2% of R&D staff working in entreprises, followed by the higher education sector employing 38,3% of R&D staff, and the public sector employing 13,5% of R&D staff. This is one indicator providing information on the significance of each stakeholder for R&D in the region and will be taken into account for the representation of the quadruple helix in the participative process of the pilot.

Economic aspects:

The economic aspects presented in this subsection have been selected for their relevance with the pilot activities of the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital region cluster: innovation, circular economy, food industry and urban agriculture.

Innovation is crucial for economic growth and has a strong regional dimension. The incentive role of the public authorities in the innovation activities business is widely recognized. In that context, the Regional Plan for Innovation 2016-2020 renews its intention to devote 3% from the gross domestic product (GDP) of the Region to fund research and development (R&D). This target value of the indicator, also called R&D intensity, constitutes one of the European objectives to be achieved by 2020. The R&D intensity in the Brussels-Capital Region is relatively modest compared to the European average, to other regions in Belgium, as well as to other European metropolitan regions. Several factors explain this regional situation. The region's economic activity is characterized in particular by a predominance of the low added-value service sector and a relative weakness of the industrial fabric of high technology.¹⁸ In terms of repartition by sector of activity (2018) in Brussels, services to enterprises represent 55% of enterprises activities in the region while industry only 3%.¹⁹

Service activities are less knowledge intensive than those of the manufacturing industry. Moreover, the interpretation of the intensity of R&D must be done with caution for a small region like Brussels-Capital, given that its economic sphere of influence extends far beyond its administrative and institutional boundaries.²⁰

Furthermore, the domain of R&I of the cluster's pilot is **circular economy**, an economic system of exchange and production which, "at all stages of the life cycle of products (goods and services), aims to increase the efficiency of the use of resources and reduce the impact on the environment while developing the well-being of individuals ". The circular economy also aims to drastically reduce the waste of resources at source while ensuring the reduction of environmental impacts and the increase in well-being. As far as possible, it develops at the local level by creating value chains that cannot be relocated. This overall definition of circular economy develops a vision of structural transformation of the Brussels economy into a low carbon economy, creating local jobs and producing added value for the people of Brussels while respecting their environment and their quality of life.

¹⁸ Peter TEIRLINCK (KU Leuven, Belspo) et André SPITHOVEN (Belspo, KU Leuven), CAHIER DE L'IBSA N°8 Flux de connaissances au sein des entreprises innovantes : le système d'innovation bruxellois DÉCEMBRE 2018 - Retrieved from Internet on 26 November:

https://ibsa.brussels/sites/default/files/publication/documents/cahiers_de_l_ibs_a_n_8_decembre_2018.pdf

¹⁹ Bruxelles Environnement, Socio-economic development of the Brussels Region - Update: February 2020 - retrived from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/l'environnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/contexte-bruxellois/developpement-socio-economique-de-la-0>

²⁰ Peter TEIRLINCK (KU Leuven, Belspo) et André SPITHOVEN (Belspo, KU Leuven), Idem

Since 2016, the Brussels-Capital region has included the transition to the circular economy in its strategic objectives which is confirmed by Alain Maron, Brussels government minister responsible for the climate transition, environment, energy and participatory democracy that declared that. "The government is determined to move forward on the environmental transition and greatly amplify the development of the circular economy.

The Regional Program in Circular Economy (PREC) has 3 general objectives:

- Transform environmental issues into economic opportunities.
- Relocate the economy to Brussels in order to produce locally when possible, reduce travel, optimize land use and create added value for the people of Brussels.
- Help create jobs.

This program includes 111 measures divided into 4 strategic parts:

- transversal measures (favorable regulatory framework, direct and indirect aid, innovation in public markets, employment, training, education)
- sectoral measures (construction, resources & waste, trade, logistics, food)
- territorial measures
- governance measures (enhanced cooperation between administrations)

In terms of **urban agriculture**, a regional strategy to increase local food production, the 'Good Food strategy' has been put in place to ensure a transition of the Brussels Region towards a more sustainable food system. It strives to respond to health, quality and environmental impact issues related to food while contributing to the development of the local economy and employment. This strategy is organised around several axes, the first of which aims to increase local and sustainable food production by stimulating agricultural production by households (vegetable gardens, henhouses, etc.) but also by professionals.²¹

c. Geographical conditions

The political, economical and human aspects of the geographical conditions of the region have been elaborated in the first subsection on societal conditions (demographic and territorial occupation) or will be detailed in the subsection dedicated to environmental aspects.

An interesting aspect to take into account for the pilot of the cluster that will be developed in the theme of circular economy and urban ecosystem is the **hydrological nature of the territory**. Brussels

²¹ Bruxelles Environnement, Good food: Professional agriculture in the Brussels region - Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/environnement-pour-une-ville-durable/good-food-agriculture>

was the valley of a river that has been buried leaving a significant impact on soil pollution. In this context, it is important to analyze the reality of Brussels vertically, looking at the layers of the sub-soil.

d. Environmental aspects:

For several years, the Region has implemented a large number of actions, at different scales (building, district, city), aimed to make Brussels a more sustainable city. The objective is to balance economic development, quality of life and solidarity while responding to the multiple environmental challenges faced by the Region.²² A number of these challenges are detailed below, selected for their relevance with the pilot activities of the TRANSFORM Brussels-Capital region cluster: spatial distribution of environmental factors, land use, quality of soil, mobility, air quality, water and aquatic environment, access to green space.

In general, all the environmental policies carried out at regional level help to increase the sustainability of the city by reducing its environmental impact (both at local and global level), by increasing its resilience and by improving the quality of life of the inhabitants of Brussels. In addition, certain actions carried out in the area of the environment are included in the framework of transversal policies carried out at different scales and which participate in the implementation of a "sustainable city" strategy, combining environmental, social and economic concerns.²³

An important element to take into account regarding the **quality of life of inhabitants of the Brussels-Capital** is the **quality of the environment unevenly distributed**. The general environment influences health in a negative way by noise, humidity, pollutants, insecurity, etc. or positively by offering places of relaxation and conviviality, etc. The quality of the habitat plays an important role but also the increase of car traffic in the city which generates significant noise pollution, degrades the air quality, is a source of insecurity for weak users and swallows up a growing part of the public space.

The **spatial distribution of environmental factors** favorable to health corresponds rather to the spatial distribution of better-off neighborhoods, while the spatial distribution of unfavorable environmental factors corresponds to the spatial distribution of disadvantaged neighborhoods.²⁴ These findings impact the orientation of the theme of the cluster's pilot, willing to address these key challenges, supporting the development of social innovations that are trying to find solutions to make the region more sustainable and looking at the problems of the urban ecosystem.

²² Bruxelles Environnement, Encironement for a sustainable city - Update: February 2020 - retrived from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/environnement-pour-une-ville-durable>

²³ Bruxelles environnement, Idem

²⁴ Myriam De Spiegelaeere, Marie-Christine Closon, Patrick Deboosere et Perrine Humblet, « Santé et qualité de vie à Bruxelles », Brussels Studies [En ligne], Notes de synthèse, mis en ligne le 10 février 2009, retrieved from Internet on 17 Novembre 2020. URL : <http://journals.openedition.org/brussels/967>; DOI : <https://doi.org/10.4000/brussels.967>

In terms of **land use, in 2019**, 60% of the plots on the territory of the region were built and 40% not. In the percentage of the plots that are built, the most important parts are occupied by apartments, buildings (15%), and houses (23%).²⁵

While the total number of buildings has slightly but steadily increased since 2001 (around +100 buildings per year on average, for a total of nearly 194,600 in 2018), a continuous change in the typology of buildings has been observed. While two-facade houses still represent more than half of the buildings in the Brussels-Capital Region, a redistribution is taking place in favor of apartment buildings, the number of which is increasing (+ 660 buildings per year on average for a total of more than 35,600 in 2018, i.e. + 46% between 2001 and 2018) to the detriment of commercial buildings and houses with two facades (on average -210 and -260 buildings per year, respectively; i.e. - 18% and - 4% between 2001 and 2018 for each category respectively).²⁶

As per the **quality of soil**, the Brussels territory, highly urbanized with a history marked by industry, has hosted - and still hosts - activities that are the source of soil and / or groundwater pollution. This pollution presents a risk to human health. Bruxelles Environnement has carried out an inventory of soils likely to be polluted. This inventory, drawn up on the basis of information concerning present and past human activities which have taken place on these sites and which are considered "at risk". The inventory included 14,520 cadastral plots registered in the soil condition inventory according to categories on 31 December 2018.²⁷

39% of plots in the region that have been included in the inventory are potentially polluted (category 0) and 25% are polluted (categories 3 or 4). This situation has an implication on citizens of the region, indeed, the validation of the inventory, which began on January 1, 2011, aimed at informing all owners and operators of land presumed to be polluted or polluted which represents approximately 35,000 people.

The TRANSFORM cluster of Brussels-Capital region would like to take this situation of **soil pollution** into account and particularly look at the fact that researchers are starting to put the emphasis on the subsoil in Brussels but rarely focus on the populations who live on the most polluted soils. There are no soil studies for example in Molenbeek when new homes are being built. The above / below ground interaction is important to consider. There is a lack of knowledge and data related to the quality of the subsoil in the region of Brussels-Capital. Something that is becoming very rare in Belgium is qualitative soil. The soils are either polluted or of unknown quality.

²⁵ Bruxelles Environnement, Land use in the Brussels Region - Update: February 2020 - retrived from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/contexte-bruxellois/occupation-du-sol-en-region-bruxelloi-0>

²⁶ Bruxelles environnement, Idem

²⁷ Bruxelles environnement, Soil condition inventory - Focus - Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/sol/inventaire-de-letat-du-sol>

In terms of **mobility**, strong changes in travel practices during the 2000s has been observed, notably with a marked increase in the use of public transport and active modes. Even if it is on the decline, the car is still mostly used by Belgians, whether in terms of number of trips (61% in 2017) or distance (74% in 2017).²⁸ In terms of “modal share for residents of the Brussels-Capital Region in number of trips”; the mode of travel in numbers of trips the most used is car (46%) followed by walking (24%) and public transport (21%).²⁹

This domination of car transportation and the significant number of vehicles in the region has a negative impact on the environment and the quality of life of inhabitants. Cars congestion and accessibility are increasingly problematic; the social acceptability of congestion is declining.

Air quality is deteriorating, in direct connection with, in particular, congestion, poor insulation of buildings and the existence of urban microclimates (heat islands). This major concern, due to its impacts on health and the environment is influenced by a large number of different pollutants. In Brussels, the quality of outdoor air has improved very significantly in recent decades and now meets current European standards in terms of emissions and concentration for the majority of pollutants. However, efforts are still needed to ensure and / or reinforce compliance with European standards relating to concentrations of fine particles (PM10) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The sources of pollution are variable (transport, heating of buildings, etc.) and, in Brussels in particular, often influenced by external contributions (pollution imported from neighboring regions)³⁰.

Another important aspect of the urban ecosystem in which the cluster will inscribe its pilot related to the urban ecosystem is the **water and aquatic environment**. In that regard, per capita water consumption is stagnating, but the consumption of water of all households is likely to increase given population growth. The current exploitation of groundwater seems reasoned and sustainable. However, the quality of one of them is contaminated by certain pollutants from human activities. Surface water also sees its quality degraded by human activities. The two Brussels stations must limit their impact by purifying the wastewater before it is discharged into the Senne. A vast upgrading project for the South station was completed at the end of 2018: the station now treats nitrogen and phosphorus but also eliminates other substances such as micro-plastics.³¹ In addition, increased waterproofing and the dilapidated and undersized condition of the pipes cause more frequent flooding and damage to the roads.

²⁸ Bruxelles environnement, Mobility and transport in the Brussels Region - Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/contexte-bruxellois/mobilite-et-transports-en-region>

²⁹ Bruxelles environnement, Idem

³⁰ Bruxelles environnement, Air - Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/air>

³¹ Bruxelles environnement, Water and aquatic environment - Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/lenvironnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/eau-et-environnement-aquatique>

Noise pollution linked to the increase in built density, problems of cohabitation between industries and housing, car congestion and the age of buildings that have been transformed from single-family houses to multiple apartments, poorly insulated. The noise perception survey carried out in 2017 at regional level highlights that the inhabitants of Brussels are bothered first by the noise of car traffic and then by air traffic. And they are 6 out of 10 to demand concrete measures.³²

Access to green space is insufficient in some cases. According to various sources (cadastre, Bruxelles-Environnement), almost half of the surface of the regional territory corresponds to green spaces. These are of diverse nature: parks, wetlands and bodies of water, woods, forests, wastelands, fields, meadows, private gardens or even large private estates. While they are all of crucial importance for the regional flora and fauna, **only green spaces accessible to the public play an important social role in terms of quality of life**, as spaces for games, meetings and relaxation. This role is particularly important at the scale of a city such as Brussels where more than 63% of the population does not have access to a private garden (INS, 2001).³³

All the observations presented in this **environmental aspects** subsection characterized the regional context of the pilot that will be developed but needs to be complemented by more recent studies, especially in the context of the **COVID 19 outbreak crisis**. In that matter, the public agency in charge of environmental questions in the region 'Bruxelles Environnement' ran a survey that analyzes the impact of the pandemic for which results were published in November 2020³⁴. Regarding the **inhabitants of Brussels and their environment**, the survey reveals that 21% of the inhabitants of Brussels do not have access to any private outdoor space, neither terrace type, nor garden type. Another interesting outcome is the fact that older people use the personal car more. The most used means of transport are public transport (37%) followed by walking (17%). Regarding **the impacts of confinement on quality of life** and on the environment, on noise, it first appears that perceptions of the noise level in Brussels are negative (before confinement): 70% of Brussels residents believe that before confinement, the city was noisy. The confinement had very positive effects on the noise level since only 16% of Brussels residents believe that the noise level in Brussels is important. Asked about the impacts of confinement on their health and their quality of life, the people of Brussels mostly expressed positive opinions. Positive opinions greatly exceed negative opinions: this is particularly the

³² Bruxelles environnement, Noise - Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November:

<https://environnement.brussels/l'environnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/bruit>

³³ Bruxelles Environnement, Green spaces: accessibility to the public- Update: February 2020 - retrieved from Internet on 23 November: <https://environnement.brussels/l'environnement-etat-des-lieux/en-detail/espaces-verts-et-biodiversite/espaces-verts-accessibilite-au>

³⁴ Bruxelles Environnement, Etude sur les opinions et les comportements des Bruxellois pour la résilience de leur ville dans le contexte de la crise sanitaire du Covid-19, Septembre 2020, retrieved from Internet on 27 November: https://letsprepare.monopinion.brussels/uploads/decidim/attachment/file/168/Bruxelles_r%C3%A9siliente_post_Covid-19_-_Pr%C3%A9sentation_finale_-_02.09.20.pdf

case for the "the ability to enjoy the environment (garden, park terrace, etc.), the feeling of quality of life in Brussels, the level of stress attributable to noise pollution and the quality of sleep. Regarding the **feelings of the decrease in urban traffic and its effects**, the results are particularly impressive: barely 8% of the people questioned declared that they had not noticed a decrease in car traffic. 75% of citizens felt an **improvement in air quality**.

To conclude, the citizens of Brussels are not particularly confident in the evolutions of the society after the Covid-19: 23% of them think that the society will be better in the future than today, 31 % think it will be a little worse, or even clearly worse. In short, even if they seem to be experiencing the crisis in a rather positive way, the people of Brussels remain worried about the future

6. Conclusions and steps ahead

All the activities carried out so far within each of the three TRANSFORM clusters have been key to the definition of the upcoming implementation of planned activities. Each of the three regions involved in TRANSFORM represents a unique ecosystem, characterised by a specific demographic distribution, specific key challenges that each region is focusing on in order to boost its R&I potential, as well as specific geographic conditions that make each cluster unique. The key element in common between all clusters is their strong commitment towards RRI, which at the level of the regional governments and funding agencies involved translates into specific actions, funding opportunities, platforms and initiatives to favour the implementation of RRI principles. For all three regions involved in the project, TRANSFORM represents a key opportunity to boost their RRI potential even further, and to assess the benefits that emerge in doing so.

The specificities of each regional framework and a deep understanding of how they affect the functioning of regional R&I are the starting point for a key next step in the project: the definition of local action plans, which are going to detail how each region is going to implement actions towards the strengthening of RRI components. Action plans will take into account outcomes of the SWOT analysis performed, looking in particular at how to address potential risks or threats and turn them into opportunities, as well as suggestions emerged from interaction with Think Tank members, which support the regional clusters in addressing all Societal, Economic, Geographical and Environmental framework conditions that have been identified.

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